

Eagle owls' predation within a highly diversified Late Glacial landscape: remains of pikas and hares (Lagomorpha) from the Loutra Almopias Cave (Central Macedonia, Greece)

Florian A. Fladerer^{1*,2}, Katerina Chatzopoulou³, Peter Steier⁴, Monika Bolka⁴, Zlatozar Boev⁵

¹ Department of Paleontology, University of Vienna, Josef-Holaubek-Platz 2 (Geozentrum), 1090 Vienna, Austria; email: florian.fladerer@univie.ac.at (* Corresponding author)

² Austrian Archaeological Institute ÖAI, Austrian Academy of Sciences, Quaternary Archeology, Hollandstraße 11-13, 1020 Vienna, Austria

³ Department of Geology, Aristotle University, School of Geology, 54124 Thessaloniki, Greece; email: katerina2c@icloud.com

⁴ VERA Laboratory, Faculty of Physics, University of Vienna, Währinger Straße 17, 1090 Vienna, Austria; e-mails: peter.steier@univie.ac.at; monika.bolka@univie.ac.at

⁵ National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria; e-mails: boev@nmnhs.com; zlatozarboev@gmail.com

(Received: 21 December 2022; accepted in revised form: 15 May 2023)

Abstract. During cave bear excavations in the Loutra Almopias Cave, Pella District, in Central Macedonia, Greece, an ecologically highly diverse Late Glacial faunal assemblage, mainly micromammals and birds, was sampled from an elevated small niche labelled LAC Ia. The lagomorphs are represented by steppe pika (*Ochotona pusilla*), brown (or European) hare (*Lepus europaeus*) and mountain hare (*Lepus timidus*). The site evidences the first record of this last species in Greece and its southernmost evidence so far. The taphonomic patterns of the fossils refer to eagle owls (*Bubo bubo*) as an accumulating agent. This is congruent with the total LAC Ia species spectrum and the bone element abundance and destruction patterns. Radiocarbon dates of $12,350 \pm 40$ ¹⁴C yrs BP (VERA-5631) from a *Lepus* sp. bone and $16,427 \pm 96$ ¹⁴C yrs BP (VERA-7402) from a *L. timidus* premolar indicate the emplacement of the assemblage in the (very probably early phase of the) Late Glacial. The taphocoenosis reflects a high variety of habitats and biodiversity from periglacial alpine grassland to deciduous forests and Mediterranean open fore-land areas with scattered brush and thick scrub. The position of the eagle owl site is approximately 50 m inside the cave. Along the distance from the Late Pleistocene entrance, the nocturnal raptors had to manage two direction changes within their flight path. That opening was closed later by talus sediments, and thus the fossil owl nest or feeding place has been sealed. The LAC Ia assemblage is so far a unique terrestrial record of Late Glacial biota in the Southern Balkans.

Fladerer, F.A., Chatzopoulou, K., Steier, P., Bolka, M., Boev, Z. 2023. Eagle owls' predation within a highly diversified Late Glacial landscape: remains of pikas and hares (Lagomorpha) from the Loutra Almopias Cave (Central Macedonia, Greece). *Geologica Balcanica* 52 (2), 3–28.

Keywords: *Ochotona pusilla*, *Lepus timidus*, *Lepus europaeus*, *Bubo bubo*, taphonomy, Voras Mountains.

INTRODUCTION

Paleontological sampling and excavations in the Loutra Almopias Cave (LAC, also Loutra Arideas

Bear Cave, or Almopia Speleopark Bear Cave) in the Pella District in Central Macedonia (Greece) started in the early 1990s and lasted until 2011 (Pappa *et al.*, 2005; Tsoukala and Rabeder, 2005;

Tsoukala *et al.*, 2006; Chatzopoulou *et al.*, 2011; Chatzopoulou, 2014; Boev and Tsoukala, 2018; Nagel *et al.*, 2019; Piskoulis, 2021).

Extant Lagomorpha species are often adapted to rather small and indicative ecological niches, and thus they are susceptible, or even vulnerable, to climatic changes (Thulin, 2003; Smith and Lissovsky, 2016; Rhenus *et al.*, 2018; Hacklander and Schai-Braun, 2019). Hence, they are extremely important for paleoecological reconstructions of the environment. Often, lagomorphs are key species in ecosystems and their presence is associated with the presence of a number of other species, *e.g.*, predators. Concerning the abundance in recent and fossil bone accumulations, pikas, hares and rabbits are among the main prey of avian predators, carnivores and humans. Body part frequencies of the prey and damage modes displayed by the bones and marks left on them often allow identification of at least part of the taphonomic history of the assemblage, and also the predator species might be identified (Andrews, 1990; Bocheński *et al.*, 1993; Bocheński, 2005; Lloveras *et al.*, 2009, 2012; Denys *et al.*, 2018; Rufà and Laroulandie, 2019).

SITE SETTING

The Loutra Almopias Cave site is located at 540 m a.s.l. in the northern part of Central Macedonia (Greece) within the municipality of Almopia, 100 km northwest of Thessaloniki (Fig. 1). A small cluster of caves lies within the southern foothills of the Voras (Boras) Mountains (Fig. 2), whose highest peak is the Kaimaki (Kaimaktsalan, 2,524 m a.s.l.), at a distance of 11.1 km from the site. From here, the view widens towards the plain of Aridaia (Almopia) or the Almopia Basin, ~200–100 m a.s.l. (Fig. 3). The cave opens in the northern cliff slope of the Nikolaou Gorge with the Thermopotamos stream, in karstified Maastrichtian limestones of the Pelagonian Zone of the Hellenides (Eleftheriadis, 2006). The cave has a passage length of ~200 m and covers 810 m² (Lazaridis and Melfos, 2021). The entrance is situated 75 m above the stream bed and it is ~3 m wide and 1.3 m high, but a second opening in the Cretaceous bedrock can be detected at ~20 m to the southeast of the modern entrance. It is closed by debris and soil, and it is assumed as the main entrance during the Late Pleistocene (Fig. 4). The cave

Fig. 1. Map of Greece (insert) and the location of the Loutra Almopias Cave (LAC; N 40°58.267', E 21°54.850') and relief map of Central Macedonia (Google Maps; accessed on 7 December 2019, modified). The LAC site is marked and the circle outlines the hypothetical hunting area of an eagle owl in the non-breeding season (here 10 km diameter) from the peaks of the Voras Mountains to the Almopia Basin (see Discussion).

Fig. 2. View from the Loutra Almopia Cave surrounding along the Nikolaou Gorge to the alpine range in the north (photo by FAF).

Fig. 3. View from the Loutra Almopia Cave surrounding along the Nikolaou Gorge with the outside basin of the Pozar thermal bath in the midground to the plain of Almopia in the south (photo by FAF).

Almopia Speleopark Bear-Cave
(Pella, Macedonia, Greece)

Ground-Map

Fig. 4. Ground map of the Loutra Almopias Cave (LAC) with the excavated squares in the chambers (Kabouroglou and Chatzitheodorou, 1999; Tsoukala *et al.*, 2006; modified). The eagle owls’ site (LAC Ia) and the reconstructed flight route (see Discussion) are marked.

is subdivided into three main chambers, LAC I to III (Tsoukala *et al.*, 2006). The site focused herein (LAC Ia) is a basin-like side niche with a diameter of about 1 m and a depth of ~0.3 m, and was filled with fine-grained sediments and bones. It is situated ~5 m above the LAC I floor, accessible across a slippery speleothem (Lazaridis and Melfos, 2021, fig. 4f). In speleological terms, it is a rising channel with a blind passage, or “window,” near the ceiling about 10 m higher than the cave-floor (Lazaridis and Melfos, 2021). No open channels or crevices are above the niche.

There are thermal springs within and close to the Almopia Speleopark area, which are caused by magmatic activity, faults and Pliocene volcanism (Eleftheriadis, 2006). This geological detail is mentioned to better understand the biological diversity addressed within the discussion and conclusion.

PREVIOUS STUDIES

The LAC Ia assemblage, composed of several thousand specimens, actually comprises, besides still un-

identified fish, amphibian and reptilian species, 55 mammalian taxa. Under this are 26 rodent, insectivore (Eulipotyphla) and Lagomorpha species (Chatzopoulou, 2014), 20 bat species (Piskoulis, 2021; Piskoulis and Chatzopoulou, 2022), seven carnivore and two ungulate species (Nagel *et al.*, 2019): *Talpa europaea*, *Sorex araneus*, *S. minutus*, *Neomys* sp., *Crociodura leucodon*, *C. suaveolens*, *Spermophilus citellus*, *Apodemus mystacinus*, *A. sylvaticus*, *A. flavicollis*, *A. uralensis*, *Cricetulus migratorius*, *Mesocricetus newtoni*, *Arvicola terrestris*, *Microtus arvalis*, *M. agrestis*, *M. (Chionomys) nivalis*, *M. (Pitymys) cf. subterraneus*, *Myodes glareolus*, *Dryomys nitedula*, *Glis glis*, *Muscardinus avellanarius*, *Spalax leucodon*, *Ochotona pusilla*, *Lepus europaeus*, *L. timidus*, *Mustela nivalis*, *M. putorius*, *Martes martes*, *M. foina*, *Canis lupus*, *Vulpes vulpes*, *Felis sylvestris*, *Capra ibex*, *Bos primigenius*. Bats are represented by *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum*, *R. mehelyi*, *R. blasii*, *R. euryale*, *R. hipposideros*, *Myotis myotis*, *M. blythii*, *M. bechsteinii*, *M. emarginatus*, *M. capaccinii*, *M. mystacinus*, *Nyctalus lasiopterus*, *N. noctula*, *N. leisleri*, *Pipistrellus pipistrellus*, *Vespertilio murinus*, *Eptesicus serotinus*, *Plecotus auritus/*

austriacus, *Barbastella barbastellus* and *Miniopterus schreibersii*. Bats are autochthonous species of the cave biotope, hence they have a limited validity for the chronological and paleoclimatological means addressed in this paper.

Fifty avian taxa, or at least 47 species, were identified in the LAC Ia assemblage by Boev and Tsoukala (2019): *Perdix perdix*, *Alectoris graeca*, *Francolinus francolinus*, *Tetrao tetrax*, *Lagopus* cf. *lagopus*, *Bonasa bonasia/Lagopus muta*, *Columba livia*, *C. palumbus*, ?*Caprimulgus* sp., *Buteo* cf. *lagopus*, *Falco* cf. *peregrinus*, *Falco* ex gr. *F. cherrug*, *Falco* cf. *tinnunculus*, *Falco* cf. *vespertinus*, *Bubo bubo*, *Athene noctua*, cf. *Otus scops*, cf. *Drycopus martius*, *Galerida* sp. cf. *cristata*, *Melanocorypha calandra*, *Alauda* sp., *Lulula arborea*, cf. *Hirundo* sp., *Riparia/Ptyonoprogne*, *Anthus* sp., *Bombycilla garrulus*, *Cinclus cinclus*, *Turdus* cf. *viscivorus*, *Sylvia* cf. *borin*, *Phoenicurus* cf. *ochruros*, *Erithacus/Luscinia* sp., *Parus major*, *Sitta* cf. *europaea*, *Garrulus glandarius*, *Pica pica*, *Pyrrhocorax graculus*, P.cf. *pyrrhocorax*, *Sturnus* cf. *vulgaris*, *Fringilla* cf. *coelebs*, *Carduelis* cf. *carduelis*, *Chloris* cf. *chloris*, *Loxia curvirostra*, *Coccothraustes coccothraustes*, *Pyrrhula pyrrhula*, *Emberiza calandra*, *Plectrophenax* cf. *nivalis*, *Emberiza* cf. *cirlus*.

Preliminary studies of the Lagomorpha remains, with a focus on the pika remains, were published by Chatzopoulou (2003, 2005), Tsoukala *et al.* (2006) and Chatzopoulou *et al.* (2011). One bone sample from the LAC Ia site, the assemblage focused on in this paper, has been integrated in a DNA molecular study of the paleogeographical distribution of *L. timidus* (Smith *et al.*, 2017).

No comprehensive statement on the significance of the LAC Ia assemblage, its timing or paleoclimatic bearing has yet been published. A time-averaged debris origin from outside the cave and even the origin as an accumulation of prey remnants from small carnivores have been supposed. Admittedly, the analysis of the avian fossils, including their destruction patterns, resulted in the explanation that, most probably, eagle owls accumulated the LAC Ia faunal remains (Boev and Tsoukala, 2019), but these authors published the time setting of the assemblage based on the radiocarbon date of 11,230±110 BP, which had been communicated to them only personally as earliest Holocene.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The total Lagomorpha sample from the five cave areas, chambers LAC I, II, III, Ib and Ia (the main

site in this analysis, Fig. 4) of the Loutra Almopias Cave, contains 47 *Ochotona* (only teeth were selected) and 98 *Lepus* specimens (cranial and postcranial specimens). They were recovered during the excavations in 1992–2006. Eight specimens were collected superficially from the floor. The teeth material was collected through washing the sediment, using sieves with a 0.8 mm grid.

Indicative lagomorph teeth are described and figured, concentrating on incisors, P2 and p3, as well as deciduous premolars from *Ochotona*. Measurements were taken with an electronic caliper with 0.1 mm precision. In the case of the teeth, the measurements were taken perpendicular to the prismatic extension. The *Ochotona* teeth were measured by using a Wild Photomakroskop M400 stereoscope with 0.001 mm precision. The morphological nomenclature of Ochotonidae is applied upon López-Martínez (1974) and López-Martínez and Thaler (1975), and the measurements (Fig. 5) are after Erbajeva and Currant (2003). We use their terms in the Leporidae chapter, where we also refer to the morphological terminology according to Hibbard (1963). Measurements of the postcranial material are in accordance with Von den Driesch (1976), but partly we follow the suggestions by Fostowicz-Frelik (2007).

We used fossil comparative *L. timidus* specimens from four Late Pleistocene sites in Austria (Table 1) and recent specimens from Norway, stored at the Department of Paleontology at the University of Vienna. From published data, the measurements from Morel and Müller (1997) of

Fig. 5. Measurements (L1 to L6) on the p3 of the Ochotonidae after Erbajeva and Currant (2003).

Table 1
Compared Late Pleistocene sites with leporids from Central Europe

Site	Assemblage accumulator	Chronology	Compared specimens	Archive
Nixloch Cave (Austria)	Mainly owls	11 ka BP (Döppes and Rabeder, 1997)	I, i, P2, p3	IPAL
Gamssulzen Cave (Austria)	Mainly owls and carnivores	14–10 ka BP (Döppes and Rabeder, 1997)	I, i, P2, p3	IPAL
Schusterlucke Cave (Austria)	Upper Palaeolithic hunter-gatherers; carnivores, owls?	Late Glacial (Döppes and Rabeder, 1997)	I, i, P2, p3	NHM GP
Knochenhöhle bei Kapellen (Cave) (Austria)	Mainly snowy owl	14 ka BP (Fladerer, 2000)	I, i, P2, p3	NHM Mam
Předmostí (Czech Republic)	Upper Palaeolithic hunter-gatherers	27–25 ka BP (Svoboda, 2008)	Three mandibles	IPAL

IPAL – Department of Paleontology, University of Vienna (PIUW); NHM GP – Museum of Natural History, Vienna, Geological-Paleontological Department; NHM Mam – Museum of Natural History, Vienna, Mammalia Collection.

Late Pleistocene, as well as recent, *L. timidus* and *L. europaeus* from Central Europe were also included. Osteological studies show that sizes and morphological features vary sometimes broadly within the species and overlap (e.g., Hauser, 1921; Koby, 1959, 1960; Angermann, 1966; Suchentrunk *et al.*, 1994). Thus, we rely here on the most indicative features as the incisors and the front premolars, and do not provide comparative measurements of the postcranial specimens.

The following abbreviations are used in figures, tables and discussions: (I) Upper incisor (DI2); (D) Upper deciduous premolar; (P) Upper premolar; (M) Upper molar; (i) Lower incisor (di2); (d) Lower deciduous premolar; (p) Lower premolar; (m) Lower molar; (Cr) Cranium; (Mx) Maxilla; (Md) Mandible; (Cox) Coxal bone; (Hu) Humerus; (Fe) Femur; (Pa) Patella; (Ul) Ulna; (Ti) Tibia; (Pa) Patella; (As) Astragalus; (Cal) Calcaneus; (Nav) Naviculare; (Cub) Cuboid; (Ses) Sesamoid; (Mc) Metacarpal; (Mt) Metatarsal; (Mp) Metapodial; (Ph) Phalanx; (sin) left; (dex) right; (compl) complete; (fr) fragment; (prox) proximal; (dist) distal; (dia) diaphysis; (manus) forefoot; (pes) hind foot; (dig) digit; (L) Length, (NISP) Number of identified specimens.

The material is stored at the School of Geology of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki under the collection label LAC (Loutra Almopias Cave) and only a small part (LAC 5124g, h, j, k) is housed at the Municipal Museum of Natural History in Aridaia.

Morphology

Ochotonidae

The steppe pika (*O. pusilla* Pallas, 1769) is represented in the LAC assemblage by deciduous and permanent teeth. Incisors from young individuals are larger towards the root of the tooth (Figs 6, 7) and have thinner enamel. The occlusal shape of the upper incisors is rectangular (Fig. 6). The anterior groove is filled with cementum only in adult individuals. The lower incisors have a trapezoidal occlusal shape (Fig. 7a). The enamel is thicker on the labial side.

The first upper premolar P3 (Fig. 6c, d) has a wide and short hypoflexus with cementum. The paraflexus is a U-shaped cement-filled fold. The upper molariform teeth (Fig. 6e, f) are divided into two nearly equal lobes by a long cement-filled hypoflexus. The upper deciduous teeth have thin enamel. In DP2, there is a deep anterior fold (Fig. 6g) with cementum, which persists along the shaft, while there is a shallower anterobuccal fold without cement. DP4 is narrower anterior than posterior, with a deep hypoflexus filled with enamel (Fig. 6h).

The first lower premolar p3 has a subtriangular occlusal shape. There are two buccal folds and one lingual filled with cement (Fig. 7d, e). The hypoflexid is wide. The anteroconid is shaped by the anteroflexid and the paraflexid. The posterior part of the tooth is more or less straight. The lower molariform teeth (Fig. 7f, g) are divided into two lobes due to the confluent hypoflexid and mesoflexid.

Fig. 6. *Ochotona pusilla*, upper teeth, Loutra Almopias Cave. a) Left incisor LAC 17468 (a1 – mesial, a2 – occlusal); b) right incisor of a young individual LAC 19827 (b1 – occlusal, b2 – alveolar); c) right P3 LAC 19822 (occlusal); d) left P3 LAC 19821 (occlusal); e) left P4/M1 LAC 18931 (occlusal); f) right M2 LAC 19836 (occlusal); g) juvenile right P2 LAC 19834 (g1 – alveolar, g2 – anterior); h) right P4 LAC 17819 (h1 – alveolar, h2 – anterior). Scale bar is 1 mm (drawing and layout by Katerina Chatzopoulou).

Fig. 7. *Ochotona pusilla*, lower teeth, Loutra Almopias Cave: a) right incisor of a young individual LAC 19805 (a1 – lateral, a2 – occlusal); b) left dp3 LAC 19855 (b1 – occlusal, b2 – lateral, b3 – lingual); c) left dp4 sin LAC 16892 (c1 – occlusal, c2 – lateral); d) right p3 LAC 19829 (occlusal); e) left p3 sin LAC 19835 (occlusal); f) right p4/m1,2 LAC 19534 (occlusal); g) right p4/m1,2 dex LAC 18954 (occlusal). Scale bar is 1 mm (drawing and layout by Katerina Chatzopoulou).

The enamel is thicker on the posterior walls of the lobes. As for the lower deciduous teeth, dp3 is elongated (Fig. 7b), with two lingual and two labial folds. The posterolingual fold is deep and persists over the length of the crown. The lingual folds are less deep and open closer to the crown base than the labial ones. The tooth has one anterior and two posterior roots; dp4 has a subrectangular occlusal shape (Fig. 7c). The mesoflexid opens closer to the

crown base than the hypoflexid. The anterior lobe is longer anteroposterior than the posterior and has a pronounced anterior protrusion. On the posterior wall of the anterior lobe, there is a prominent posterior directed V-shaped ridge. The tooth has two anterior and two posterior roots.

Briefly addressing the variability of the shape of the LAC third lower premolar (Table 2, measurement L2), it is narrower than in *O. pusilla angustifrons*

Table 2

Ochotona pusilla from the Loutra Almopias Cave. Measurements (see Fig. 5) of p3 in mm compared with fossil and extant subspecies

	n	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6
LAC 19829	1	1.13	1.28	0.41	0.71	0.46	0.28
LAC 19835	1	1.02	1.04	0.35	0.64	0.31	0.26
<i>O. pusilla</i> [*]	25	0.95–1.2	1.0–1.5	0.3–0.5	0.6–0.75	0.35–0.6	0.2–0.3
<i>O. pusilla occidentalis</i> ¹	10	1.07	1.15	0.38	0.7	0.4	0.26
<i>O. pusilla spelea</i> ²	12	1.0–1.1	1.0–1.3	0.4–0.5	0.7–0.8	0.4–0.5	0.3–0.4
<i>O. pusilla angustifrons</i> ^{2*}		1.1	1.4				

¹ Erbajeva et al. (2001); ² Erbajeva and Currant (2003); *extant (from the same publications).

Fig. 8. *Ochotona pusilla* from the Loutra Almopias Cave LAC Ia and from the LAC III floor. Scatter diagram of upper incisor dimensions (measurements are taken on the occlusal portion). The distribution is function of the individual age, showing that juvenile pikas have been frequently caught by the eagle owls (diagram by Katerina Chatzopoulou).

frons (Erbajeva and Curren, 2003). The posterior border of the LAC p3s is straight, whereas in *O. pusilla angustifrons* this is apparently convex. *O. pusilla occidentalis* (Erbajeva *et al.*, 2001) from France shows a wide confluence between the anteroconid and the posteroconid of p3, whereas in the LAC specimens the anteroconid is less confluent with the rest of the tooth. The measurements also do not significantly differ from *O. pusilla spelea* (Table 4). Research has shown a rather wide intraspecific variability of *O. pusilla* during the Pleistocene for its representatives dispersed over vast steppe and mountainous areas of Europe (Rabiniak *et al.*, 2023). Thus, from the LAC Ia material, an attribution to a subspecies level is not possible. Numerous *Ochotona* teeth are from young individuals (Fig. 8).

Leporidae

The LAC Ia assemblage contains 94 *Lepus* specimens, and further four were recovered from the sediments of the cave floor, but the majority of the specimens do not allow a species attribution (Tables 3, 4).

Upper incisor (DI2) (Figs 9a, 11), LAC 18923, has a large quadratic shape with thick enamel, a rounded interior edge and a cementum-filled groove. The shape and the enamel thickness are the most distinct characteristics of *L. timidus*, whereas the other two characteristics are more subjected to

Table 3

Lepus cranial and further dental specimens from the Loutra Almopias Cave

	LAC Ia	LAC II	LAC III
Cranial fragments	1	–	–
DI2	4	–	–
P2	6	–	–
P4	–	–	1
di2	6	–	–
p3	7	1	–

Table 4

Lepus postcranial specimens from the Loutra Almopias Cave

	LAC Ia	LAC I	LAC III
Humerus	4	–	1
Radius	–	–	–
Ulna	1	–	–
Metacarpalia	7	–	–
Phalanges manus	2	–	–
Vertebrae	1	–	–
Coxal bone	4	–	–
Femur	3	–	–
Tibiofibula	9	1	–
Patella	2	–	–
Calcaneus	6	–	–
Talus/Astragalus	1	–	–
Cuboid	1	–	–
Naviculare	1	–	–
Metatarsalia	16	–	–
Phalanges pedis	12	–	–

Fig. 9. *Lepus timidus* and *L. europaeus* from the Loutra Almopias Cave, upper incisors (DI2). *L. timidus*: a) right incisor LAC 18923 (a1 – occlusal, a2 – lateral). *L. europaeus*: b) right incisor LAC 19794 (b1 – occlusal, b2 – lateral); c) left incisor LAC 18922 (c1 – occlusal, c2 – lateral). Scale bar is 1 mm (drawing and layout by Katerina Chatzopoulou).

Fig. 10. *L. europaeus* and *Lepus* sp. from the Loutra Almopias Cave, lower incisors (di2). *L. europaeus*: a) right incisor LAC 19780 (a1 – occlusal, a2 – lateral); b) left incisor LAC 19801 (b1 – occlusal, b2 – lateral); c) left incisor LAC 19807 (occlusal); d) right incisor LAC 19808 (occlusal); e) right incisor LAC 19806 (occlusal). *Lepus* sp. (juvenile): f) right incisor LAC 19805 (alveolar). Scale bar is 1 mm (drawing and layout by Katerina Chatzopoulou).

Fig. 11. *Lepus timidus* and *L. europaeus*. Measurements of the upper incisor (DI2) from the Loutra Almopias Cave LAC Ia compared to recent and Late Pleistocene samples (LG – Late Glacial) of *L. timidus* and *L. europaeus*. *L. timidus* from Champreveyres, Switzerland (Morel and Müller, 1997), *L. europaeus* from the Nixloch site, Austria (Fladerer, 1992), from collections at the University of Tübingen, Germany, P. Morel's collection (Morel and Müller, 1997), and one individual at the Aristotle University, Thessaloniki. Different occlusal and alveolar measurements of the same incisor are connected by a line (diagram by Katerina Chatzopoulou).

Fig. 12. *Lepus timidus* and *L. europaeus*. Measurements of lower incisor (di2) from the Loutra Almopias Cave LAC Ia compared to recent and Late Pleistocene findings (LG – Late Glacial). *L. timidus* from Champréveyres, Switzerland (P. Morel’s collection, Morel and Müller, 1997), from Nixloch, Austria (Fladerer, 1992); *L. europaeus* from the Knochenhöhle bei Kapellen site, Austria (unpublished data), from collections at the University of Tübingen, Germany, P. Morel’s collections (Morel and Müller, 1997) and recent individuals at the Aristotle University, Thessaloniki. Different occlusal and alveolar measurements of the same incisor are connected by a line (diagram by Katerina Chatzopoulou).

variability (e.g., Hauser, 1921; Koby, 1960; Morel and Müller, 1997). LAC 19794 (Fig. 9b) is a buccal-lingual much shorter incisor with thin enamel. A third specimen is also rather extended mesio-distally. It has a wide U-shaped groove (Fig. 9c). These two specimens are attributed to *L. europaeus*.

Lower incisors (di2) (Figs 10, 12): All five adult lower incisors are trapezoid-shaped and the length-width ratio is wider than a rectangular. Thus, they are all within the published *L. europaeus* range or very close to it. The juvenile specimen LAC 19805 (Fig. 10f) cannot be attributed to any species.

Foremost upper premolar P2 (Fig. 13): The six specimens show the typical occlusal pattern of leporids with three mesial folds or grooves: a deep paraflexus (main fold), a more variable hypoflexus (internal fold, mesiolingual fold) and a shallow to more distinct mesoflexus (anteroexternal fold, mesio-buccal fold). Four specimens of the six have a deep mesiolingual fold (LAC 18919, LAC 18920, LAC 19819, LAC 19825) and it is short and narrow with thick enamel in LAC 18918, while it is

short and wide with thin enamel in LAC 19795. The mesiobuccal fold is distinctly V-shaped in five cases and only one has a shallow groove. Based on published observations (Koby, 1959, 1960) and the samples observed by the first author, the deep V-shaped fold seems much more frequent in *L. europaeus*. The mesial-distal thickness of the tooth compared to the buccal-lingual width and the enamel is frequently thicker in *L. timidus*.

Foremost lower premolar p3 (Fig. 14): The shape of the eight specimens of p3 varies from a subround diameter (Fig. 14b, LAC 18945) of the prismatic tooth to a mesio-distally stretched appearance in LAC 19782 (Fig. 14e) and LAC 19781 (Fig. 14g). All eight specimens have an anteroflexid (mesial reentrant, anterior fold), but three also have a paraflexid (anterolingual fold), two of which with a cement filling. The protoflexid (anterobuccal fold) shows variability from a simple, broad groove to a nearly regular fourfold plication. The most distinct dichotomy is shown by the hypoflexid (posterior buccal fold, buccal main fold): the thick anterior

enamel wall is more or less plicated in five specimens (Fig. 14c–g) and more or less smooth, without undulations in three (Fig. 14a, b, h). Regarding the known spectra of p3-variants of *L. europaeus* within a limited geographical region (Suchentrunk *et al.*, 1994), it seems speculative to contribute single specimens to a morphospecies. Otherwise, the

Fig. 13. *Lepus* from the Loutra Almopias Cave, upper first premolar (occlusal view). *L. timidus*: a) right P2 LAC 18919. *L. europaeus*: b) right P2 LAC 18918; c) left P2 LAC 19819. *Lepus* sp.: d) right P2 LAC 18920; e) left P2 LAC 19825; f) left P2 LAC 19795. Scale bar is 1 mm (drawing and layout by Katerina Chatzopoulou).

Fig. 14. *Lepus* from the Loutra Almopias Cave, lower first premolar (occlusal view): a) *L. timidus* right p3 LAC 18944; b) *Lepus* cf. *timidus* left p3 LAC 18945; c–f) *L. europaeus* (c – Left p3 LAC 17099, d – left p3 LAC 18946, e – left p3 LAC 19782; f – right p3 LAC 19796); g) *Lepus* cf. *europaeus* left p3 LAC 19781; h) *Lepus* sp. left p3 LAC 19783. Scale bar is 1 mm (drawing and layout by Katerina Chatzopoulou).

L. timidus p3 occlusal pattern is characterized by its simplicity. Angermann (1966) could not observe any specimen with plications of the hypoflexid within a sample of 118 individuals.

The cranial fragment LAC 3875, the maxillary part of a palatine bridge with parts of the alveoli of the P2, P3 and P4 (Fig. 15), deserves close attention: its width between the P3 measures 16 mm, and the length is 6.3 mm. Comparisons by F. Suchentrunk (pers. comm.) show that both measures are rather high and this speaks explicitly in favor of attribution to *L. timidus* (Fig. 16). This is supported by the large *L. timidus* P3 (LAC 18944, Fig. 14a). The relative palatal bridge length shows a broad variation, as many characteristics in *Lepus* species, but the means are slightly greater in *L. timidus* compared to *L. europaeus* (Suchentrunk and Davidovic, 2004, fig. 2).

Postcranial bones: The LAC Ia leporid sample contains 70 specimens. These are preserved mainly fragmented, with the exception of the coxal and the tarsal bones, few metapodials and the phalanges. Among the long limb bones only one right femur (LAC 5124h, Fig. 17) and one right tibia (LAC 5253a) are exceptions that exceed 10 cm. Two further long limb bones in the total LAC sample must be mentioned: a *Lepus* humerus from the cave floor in LAC III (LAC 7501a, L=108.6 mm, Fig. 17) and one tibiofibula (LAC 7501b) with the proximal parts

Fig. 15. *Lepus* cf. *timidus* palatine bridge fragment LAC 3875 from the Loutra Almopias Cave, LAC Ia site (a – dorsal view, b – ventral view). Scale bar is 1 cm.

Fig. 16. Tentative diagram of the palatal bridge, palatal width to length in mm, based on 28 *L. europaeus* and *L. timidus* specimens. White circles are *L. europaeus* specimens from Central Europe (BG – Baumgarten, LA – Lasse, STR – Stripfing, ZW – Zwerndorf, all four in Lower Austria; BK – Bulskamp, MB – Moerbeke, SL – Sint Niklaas, all three in Belgium), black dots are *L. timidus* specimens (CH – Switzerland, *L. timidus varronis*, PIUW – North Norway, *L. t. timidus*), LAC – Loutra Almopias Cave. By courtesy of F. Suchentrunk, University of Veterinary Medicine Vienna, Department of Integrative Biology and Evolution.

Fig. 17. Identified postcranial *Lepus* bone specimens from the Loutra Almopias Cave.

Fig.18. *Lepus* sp. from the Loutra Almopias Cave: a) coxa fragment dex LAC 4322 (lateral view); b) coxa fragment dex LAC 3876 (lateral view), both with punctured marks. Scale bar is 1 cm.

missing from LAC Ib. Most frequent in the LAC Ia sample are distal fragments, namely nine. A navicular and a cuboid tarsal (LAC 3858–3859) are rather slender compared to our *L. timidus* specimens and we suggest that they belong more possibly to the brown hare, for the mountain hare has more robust wrists. Three second phalanges (LAC 1875, 1876, 1877) are conspicuously long. We justify their attribution to *L. timidus* on the basis of the longer hand and foot length, which is mainly due to the observed greater lengths of the phalanges (Hauser, 1921). The four coxal bones in the sample – which are very significant in taphonomic terms – cannot be attributed to either of the two species (Fig. 18).

Taphonomy

Skeletal elements and age preference

In the *Ochotona* sample, 16 deciduous premolars are found within a total sample of 31 cheek teeth, which is more than 50%. Furthermore, nine of 12 upper incisor specimens represent juvenile individuals, as it is indicated by their smaller occlusal surface than their alveolar measures (Fig. 8). The measurements corroborate the observation and indicate that younger individuals were more frequently preyed on.

The *Lepus* sample includes almost 100 specimens and it contains highly fragmented skull and

mandible parts, represented by isolated teeth, as well as coxal bones (innominate), long limb bones and parts of the front and hind paws (Table 4). Only one vertebra is part of the sample, but this is very probably biased by the sampling, and also ribs have not been sorted because of their negligible diagnostic value.

Concerning the individual age composition of the leporid remains, a significant preference for juvenile individuals cannot be traced and this contrasts with the observation of the ochotonid remains. Only one single distal metatarsal epiphysis indicates a juvenile hare individual beside several unclear postcranial specimens. Among the dental loci, one lower incisor is from a second young individual of *Lepus* cf. *europaeus*. Furthermore, a distal tibia fragment exhibits a very thin crevice at the position of the epiphyseal suture and attests to this individual as not being fully adult. One metapodial exhibits pathology, and thus belongs to an injured individual, which could fall easier prey to raptors.

The LAC Ia sample does not include any undamaged complete long limb bones. Distal ends, shafts or distal fragments are dominant and undamaged proximal epiphyses are subordinate. Out of a total of 15 studied specimens (humeri, femora and tibi-fibulae), ten limb bones are represented by distal parts and five with proximal parts preserved, and all these also show macroscopic damage. High completeness can be reported from calcanei, metatarsals

and proximal phalanges. They are the most compact bones in the lagomorph skeleton. The sample contains four coxal bones and all of them have the ilium at least partly preserved. All the bones from the hind limb (NISP 52) highly outnumber the specimens from the front limb (NISP 15).

Damage marks

The most apparent modification signs on the leporid skeletal elements are punctured marks as seen on the ulna (Fig. 17), the coxal bones (Fig. 18) and the calcanei (Fig. 19): the destruction of the olecranon ulnae can be regarded as a characteristic signature of a raptor's beak in order to get on the strong triceps-muscle; the crista iliaca of all four coxae are damaged by puncture edging, and five out of six *Lepus calcanei* show these marks on the tuber. The most frequent breaks of the bones are transverse stepped or hinged type, which means destruction of the fresh bone, at least partly by forceful pulling away the muscles with the beak. In many cases, the edges are slightly polished, especially when the edges are prominent. This is very probably caused by trampling within the nest, the effect of bone-to-bone or bone-to-sediment movements when the partly heavy owls were present at the site (compare Andrews, 1990).

No case of tooth marks can be reported, which would be an alternative indication of influence by smaller carnivores. No shaft splinters and no chewed articulation ends are present, which similarly would indicate carnivores as taphonomic agents. There is no corrosive digestion marking on

the bone surfaces, and no peculiar scratch marks or other signs of sediment transport can be identified. Especially this last proves the *in-situ* origin of the taphocoenosis and contradicts earlier opinions by authors about an allochthonous or transported origin and accumulation of Late Pleistocene and Holocene bones from outside the cave over time. Some cases of scratching can be observed. They originate very probably in the course of holding prey parts with the claws and dismemberment with the beak by pulling the head upwards, or by trampling.

Radiocarbon dating

Five AMS ^{14}C dates from three LAC Ia samples are available (Table 5, Fig. 20). Collagen from these animal samples was extracted and purified with the "modified Longin" method, *i.e.*, the Longin procedure (Longin, 1971) was extended by a NaOH and subsequent HCl treatment before gelatinization, and the extraction yield determined. Collagen yield >1% of the initial sample amount and the C/N ratio were determined as an indication of reliable ^{14}C dates. These parameters were determined with an elemental analyzer coupled to an IonPlus AGE-3 graphitization unit. The ^{14}C measurement was performed following the VERA protocol for routine measurements (Steier *et al.*, 2004).

Two of the dates were already cited by previous studies (Nagel *et al.*, 2019). The first was made during the cave bear excavation campaigns on a sample of bones from micromammals, which produced an age of $11,230 \pm 110$ ^{14}C yrs BP (VERA-0060). In order to get a more precise dating in the early phase of this study, we selected a *Lepus* tibia (sample LAC 3879), which gave an age of $12,350 \pm 40$ ^{14}C yrs BP (VERA-5631). In the course of the research, it became evident that the assemblage contains bat bones from different ages, and one selected bone specimen from a bat did not contain collagen, as communicated by the Groningen lab (Piskoulis, 2021). The second date, obtained from a *Lepus* bone points to the Bølling early warm phase of the Bølling-Allerød interstadial. The archived graphite of the two processed samples was recently re-dated for control and the results were consistent with the primary dating. Recently, a third sample, the *L. timidus* specimen LAC 18944, a first premolar with a small fragment of the mandible, was selected. This specimen has been tested by molecular genetics as *L. timidus* (Smith *et al.*, 2017). The collagen content was 10.7% and the C/N ratio 2.5. This sample brought out a ^{14}C age of $16,427 \pm 96$ ^{14}C yrs BP (VERA-7402).

Fig. 19. *Lepus* sp. from the Loutra Almopias Cave. Calcaneus sin LAC 3878 (medial view) with puncture marks on the tuber. Scale bar is 1 cm.

Table 5

Loutra Almpia Cave LAC Ia site radiocarbon dating results. ¹⁾ 1σ – uncertainty; ²⁾ determined with the AMS system. The $\delta^{13}C$ values may be altered during sample preparation, thus they are suited only for quality control, and not for extended interpretation; ³⁾ calculated with OxCal v4.4.4 (Bronk Ramsey, 2021), <https://c14.arch.ox.ac.uk/oxcal/OxCal.html> (accessed on 20 March 2023) and the IntCal20 calibration curve (Reimer et al., 2020). The data correspond to the 2σ -confidence level. Probability of the individual time periods in brackets.

Lab. Nr.	Sample name	$\delta^{13}C^{1,2}$ [‰]	^{14}C age ¹⁾ [BP]	Calibrated age ³⁾
VERA-0060_2	Sample of small vertebrates from LAC Ia	-20.9 ± 1.4	$11,359 \pm 52$	13,333–13,157 calBP (93.3%) 13,139–13,121 calBP (2.1%)
VERA-0060		-17.5 ± 1.8	$11,230 \pm 110$	13,335–12,894 calBP (95.2%) 12,855–12,850 calBP (0.2%)
VERA-5631B	LAC 3879 <i>Lepus</i> sp. tibia	-14.5 ± 0.7	$12,463 \pm 37$	14,959–14,773 calBP (27.6%) 14,743–14,328 calBP (67.8%)
VERA-5631		-18.8 ± 0.7	$12,350 \pm 40$	14,828–14,689 calBP (23.1%) 14,560–14,145 calBP (72.3%)
VERA-7402	LAC 18944 <i>L. timidus</i> P3inf	-24.5 ± 1.9	$16,427 \pm 96$	20,097–19,561 calBP (95.4%)

OxCal v4.4.4 Bronk Ramsey (2021); r.5 Atmospheric data from Reimer et al (2020)

Fig. 20. Calibration plot of five ^{14}C measurements from three samples from the Loutra Almpias Cave microvertebrate assemblage LAC Ia (Reimer et al., 2020; <https://c14.arch.ox.ac.uk/oxcal/OxCal.html>, accessed on 6 December 2022). VERA-7402 is a *L. timidus* specimen, LAC-3879 is a sample of *Lepus* sp., and VERA-0060 is a mixed sample of microvertebrates.

***Bubo bubo* as taphonomic agent**

The skeletal part abundance of the lagomorph sample and the frequency of punctured destruction marks, the lack of typical tooth marks on the bones traces of chewing or gnawing and biting, and the positive abundance of more distal fragments than diaphysal splinters speak clearly in favor of a large nocturnal avian predator. Diurnal raptors like eagles do not fly into caves. The role of small to medium-sized carnivores like foxes or mustelids can be ex-

cluded because typical marks and breakage patterns are missing. It is characteristic of these predators that they do not accumulate remains of their prey in the same place in significant quantities, especially of small victims, such as we have in this case. Other approaches, such as the high frequency of preyed bird species (Boev and Tsoukala, 2019), who also first published the result that the bird assemblage has most probably been produced by *Bubo bubo*. Bone remains of eagle owls were found in the cave and so far unstudied amphibian, reptilian and fish

species exclude any other accumulator than large owls. Four owl species were identified (Boev and Tsoukala, 2019), but among these only *Bubo bubo* actively uses the deep inner parts of caves (e.g., Andrews, 1990). On the other hand, the extremely wide size range of established prey excludes other small owls that inhabit caves. Glirids, which form part of the LAC Ia taphocoenosis (Chatzopoulou, 2014), are usually rare in carnivore dens (Andrews, 1990). Many of the mammalian species that fall prey to the eagle owls show a distinct nocturnal or crepuscular activity, and the steppe pika (e.g., Smith and Lissovsky, 2016) and both *Lepus* species do so (Smith *et al.*, 2010; Hacklander and Schai-Braun, 2019). The total destruction patterns on the leporid specimens and the paucity of signatures of digestion (Bocheński, 2005) in the LAC leporid sample speak clearly in favor of the largest owl species as taphonomic main agent. *Bubo bubo* is actually represented in the bone sample by five phalanges (Boev and Tsoukala, 2019), and all these data allow to identify the LAC Ia niche site as an eagle owl site, where the birds landed with the caught prey, ate it and rested there. It is also very probable that the site was a nest.

The LAC Ia leporid sample contains a high number of postcranial specimens and the majority are from the hind limb. It is striking that distal ends, shafts or distal fragments are dominant and only the most solid parts of the proximal epiphyses are present and these show punctured damage (see above). This corroborates the observation of fossil, historical and recent taphocoenoses with leporid bones that were produced by eagle owls (De Cupere *et al.*, 2009; Lloveras *et al.*, 2009, 2012; Rufà and Laroulandie, 2019). The relative abundance data from recent eagle owl nests and the analyzed breakage patterns in Lloveras *et al.* (2012) show a remarkably high concordance with the LAC Ia leporid sample: a predominance of postcranial material, mainly from the hind limb, a moderate breakage intensity with nearly complete tibiae, complete calcanei, metatarsals and proximal phalanges, and a low intensity of digestion signatures. This indicates that the remains do not derive from pellets, at least part of them. Eagle owl parents do not emit pellets into the nest: the patterns observed from eagle owl pellets by Hockett and Haws (2002) are somewhat different, as these authors found higher percentages of forelimb bones. The frequently punctured innominates are a strong indication of damage by owls (Hockett, 1991; Hockett and Haws, 2002). The destruction of the olecranon of the ulna is also congruent with the observations from *Bubo* sites (De Cupere *et al.*, 2009, fig.3). The LAC Ia assemblage contains also

small postcranial parts, mainly from distal limbs from *Capra ibex*, *Bos taurus* and *Cervus elaphus*, and cranial as well as limb parts from smaller carnivores (Nagel *et al.*, 2019). This is consistent with other (sub)fossil roost or nest assemblages and observations of living Eurasian eagle owls. They are known for their broad prey spectrum that comprises beetles and carcasses from big mammals, and even successful attacks on weakened ungulates and smaller carnivores have been reported (Jánosy and Schmidt, 1970; Andrews, 1990; Papageorgiou *et al.*, 1993; Simeonov *et al.* 1998; Penteriani *et al.*, 2001; Lourenço, 2006; Sándor and Ionesco, 2009; Lloveras *et al.*, 2009). The eagle owl is probably the bird with the widest prey spectrum. Trampling marks could also be observed on LAC Ia bones. It is plausible that the parental birds weighing up to more than 4.6 kg during their breeding and feeding activity compress the nest material.

Nests and roosts of *Bubo bubo* have frequently been observed in rocky areas and cave entrances (e.g., Andrews, 1990; Papageorgiou *et al.*, 1993; Penteriani *et al.*, 2001), so that the LAC Ia site would be a rather rare document of eagle owls flying into deep cave parts, along an evident distance of several 50 m, including two changes of direction and turns (Fig. 4). No corroborative reference of an actual observation of a nest so far within a cave could be found by the authors, but the case is definitely possible (V. Penteriani, pers. comm.) as eagle owls have an extraordinary vision capacity in the darkness and are very adaptable birds. One might assume that, besides the actual small entrance, in the past there was an open crevice in some part of the ceiling of the cave, through which more light could have penetrated to facilitate the visual orientation of the birds, but there is no indication to support the presence of any further opening besides the actual entrance and the Late Pleistocene southern opening (G. Lazaridis, pers. comm.).

As a further result of these observations, also the bird specimens from the floor chambers of the Loutra Almopias Cave, published and assigned “to the Late Pleistocene (37,800 yrs \pm 370/360 BP)” by Boev and Tsoukala (2019) besides the LAC Ia assemblage, could be remnants of the activity of the Late Glacial owls. This radiocarbon date is made from a cave bear femur (*Ursus spelaeus* group or *U. ingressus*, see Rabeder *et al.*, 2006) and has the lab number GrN-7573 (Nagel *et al.*, 2019). The bear specimens excavated from the sediments in the cave-floor have a rather different preservation than the birds (see Pappa *et al.*, 2005; Tsoukala *et al.* 2006). Parts of the preyed animals by the LAC

Ia owls could have been lost during the flight in the cave. The fact that the preservation of these fossils from the floor is not different from the LAC Ia specimens supports this hypothesis.

DISCUSSION

The occurrence of lagomorphs

The extant steppe pika is a mainly burrowing steppe-dwelling lagomorph (Smith and Lissovky, 2016). Paleoclimatically, at least from a Western and Central European perspective, Late Pleistocene pika findings are significant for glacial and stadial dry periods, and they speak in favor of steppe environments. The abundance in cave sediments is also interpreted as reflecting habitats with cliffy shelters and habitats of the predators of the ochotonas (*e.g.*, Jánossy, 1986; Fladerer, 1992; Frelík and Felík, 2010).

In the northern Balkans, *O. pusilla* occurs in Late Pleistocene sediments from Pećina the Cave (Dalmatia), Šandalja (Istria) and Vindija Cave (Croatia) (Malez, 1979, 1986), Smolučka Cave (Dimitrijević, 1991, 1997), Gradašnica Cave (Marković, 2008), Mirilovska Cave (Dimitrijević and Jovanović, 2002), Vrelska Cave (Marković and Pavlović, 1991). The southern and eastern Balkans are within the southern distribution area of the steppe pika during the Late Pleistocene. In Bulgaria, its occurrence is continuous from the Middle Pleistocene layers in the Morovitsa Cave (Popov, 1989), through the Late Pleistocene in the Temnata Cave (Popov, 1994) and Cave 16 (Popov, 2000), until the early Holocene in Cave 15 (Popov, 2000) and Madara (Mitev and Boev, 2006; Mitev, 2016). A Late Glacial record is also from the Gornja Bijambar Cave in Bosnia (Dimitrijević, 1988, 1991).

In Greece, *O. pusilla* is reported so far from Arnissa, dated to the penultimate (Saalian/Rissian) Glacial (Mayhew, 1978). More recently, a mandible fragment from Paleolithic layers in the Sarakenos Cave in Central Greece has been attributed to the pika (Wilczyński *et al.*, 2016), but the first author of the paper counter-checked the specimen as a response to our questioning and apologized for the incorrect determination (J. Wilczyński, pers. comm.).

Hares of the genus *Lepus* extended from Asia into Europe in the earliest Pleistocene, and are named as *L. terraerubrae* and/or *L. praetimidus* (Jánossy, 1969, 1986; Fladerer, 1984, 1987). They show molar pattern characteristics that are closely related to the later *L. timidus*, and the populations

persist throughout the Middle Pleistocene (Fostowicz-Frelík and Gasparik, 2006).

Lepus timidus' Late Pleistocene distribution is broadly consistent with the Mammoth steppe biome from Western to Eastern Europe and finds are frequently reported from larger Upper Paleolithic open-air camp sites and cave sites, including human-influenced assemblages (*e.g.*, Koby, 1960; Mottl, 1975; López-Martínez, 1980; Morel and Müller, 1997; Fladerer, 2000; Fladerer and Salcher-Jedrasiak, 2008; Veitschegger *et al.*, 2015 for Central European sites). The record toward Southeastern Europe is markedly fading. Only few reports from the last glaciation from Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Montenegro mention the species (Malez, 1986; Bogičević and Dimitrijević, 2004; Mihailović, 2009). A synopsis by Dimitrijević (1997) of Serbian cave sites does not yet report evidence of *L. timidus*, but from eastern Serbia later a single site is proven (Dimitrijević and Jovanović, 2002). From the eastern Balkans, it is cited from La Adam in Romania (Dumitrescu *et al.*, 1963), and in Bulgaria the species is reported from the Middle and Late Pleistocene (Popov, 1908, 1909; Markov, 1951; Nikolov, 1983). Several attributions to *L. timidus* from the Dinaric Alps, the northern and central Balkans were reassessed and finally identified as *L. europaeus* (Miracle and Brajković, 2010).

Concerning Greece, Melentis (1969) attributed a maxilla fragment from the Limnon Cave on the Peloponnese to *L. timidus*, but the figured specimen does not allow a closer determination than *Lepus* sp. and our taphonomic re-assessment of the reported data evaluates the determination as a Pleistocene specimen as speculative, and thus this locality has to be deleted from a hypothetical distribution. Similarly, the *Lepus* specimens from Arnissa could not be more closely determined than to genus level (Mayhew, 1978). Thus, the Loutra Almopias Cave sample provides the first evidence of *L. timidus* in Greece. Based on the morphological determination, the mountain hare premolar (LAC 18944, Fig. 14a) has been later analyzed within a mitochondrial DNA study on the Pleistocene origins of modern European populations of the species and a successful sequencing confirmed it as *L. timidus* (Smith *et al.*, 2017). This specimen has recently been destroyed in order to get an indicative ¹⁴C-date (see Radiocarbon dating).

The first appearance of *L. europaeus* is reported from the Lower Pleistocene of the Caucasus and only a few Middle to early Late Pleistocene records from Eastern Europe are available (Jánossy, 1986; Averianov, 2001). In the Late Pleistocene, only

these two leporid species were present between NW and SE Europe. One of the most prominent morphological characteristics is the more complicated occlusal premolar pattern that seems to make the brown hare's feeding on grasses more efficient and makes it more successful in direct competition with the mountain hare. Ecologically – on a rough scale – the preferred habitats of mountain hares are the tundra and the boreal and alpine regions (Smith *et al.*, 2010), whereas brown hares are apparently more flexible in habitats (Hacklander and Schai-Braun, 2019). Hybridization of the two species is well known in overlapping areas (*e.g.*, Thulin, 2003). The brown hare could probably find more refuge in the Balkans during the stadial periods (Miracle *et al.*, 2010). A permanent distribution from the mid-Late Pleistocene into the Holocene seems plausible as genetic research has shown that Central Europe has been repopulated by brown hares from the Balkans (Djan *et al.*, 2017) very probably through successful competition with the resident mountain hare.

The resourceful accumulator

Fossil assemblages from prehistoric to historic sites in Western, Central and Southern Europe with lagomorph remains can be attributed to *Bubo bubo* activity, partly distinguishable as roost or nest sites (Jánossy and Schmidt, 1970; Andrews, 1990; De Cupere *et al.*, 2009; Lloveras *et al.*, 2009). The Eurasian eagle owl is the largest nocturnal bird; its wingspan reaches 1.8 m, and the individuals hunt over a large area, up to 10 km in diameter (Andrews, 1990). This indication we used for the sketch in Fig. 1. Recent telemetry monitoring found individual movements per day during the nestling period in summer of close to 20 km (Heggøy *et al.*, 2021), but these authors observed also that home-ranges are smaller in territories with higher prey density. The broad species spectrum of the LAC Ia assemblage speaks in favor of this. The taphonomic analysis and the radiocarbon dates give no answer to how many individuals or generations accumulated the LAC Ia sample. The three differing dates may speak in favor of an interruption or the re-use of an abandoned site.

Concerning the LAC Ia species list, with the exception of bat species which are cave-dwellers, we have no doubt that all these specimens were brought in by owls during the early Late Glacial (or the radiocarbon dated interval if we do not evaluate the dates). The eagle owls may catch also tree-hollow-dwelling bats and regurgitate finally their pellets in the cave. Thus, bats may be part of the prey spec-

trum of the eagle owls (*e.g.*, Jánossy and Schmidt, 1970; Papageorgiou *et al.*, 1993; Sándor and Ionesco, 2009), but the distinction between killed and at-the-place died individuals is almost impossible for the specialist except above mentioned cases (compare Piskoulis, 2021).

The radiocarbon dating results of the taphocenosis (Table 5) differ. On the other hand, the number of hare bones is only 94, and the number of bird bones is 551, which rather supports the hypothesis of the relatively short-lived existence of the owl feeding place. These bone finds, as herein established examples, could have come from no fewer than six hares and 68 preyed birds. Hence, 68 to 551 avian prey items of the eagle owl could be caught without considering other prey in no more than two years. Taking hypothetically into account an ephemeral and short-term emplacement of the owl site, the most recent dating of the *L. timidus* specimen LAC 18944 (see Radiocarbon dating) is herein interpreted as the most precise of the small data set, and thus as support of this hypothesis.

CONCLUSIONS

During the Last Glacial maximum (LGM) in the Dinaric and the Albanian Alps southwards of the southern Balkan Peninsula, massive and smaller glaciers had existed and they have very probably persisted into the Late Glacial, or reappeared during its cold phases (Messerli, 1967; Hughes, 2004; Lawson *et al.*, 2004; Woodward *et al.*, 2004; Hughes *et al.*, 2006; Kuhlemann *et al.*, 2009). Based on our results periglacial open vegetation in the alpine and subalpine altitudes of the Voras Mountains can be reconstructed. It provided forage for cold-adapted species like the Alpine chough (*Pyrrhocorax graculus*), the snow bunting (*Plectrophenax nivalis*), the snow vole (*Microtus nivalis*), the steppe pika (*Ochotona pusilla*) and the mountain hare (*Lepus timidus*). The richly structured landscape reconstruction includes climatically favored talus slopes preferred by rock partridge (*Alectoris graeca*), alpine to subalpine conifer forest as habitats of the willow ptarmigan (*Lagopus lagopus*), the hazel grouse (*Bonasa bonasia*), the black grouse (*Tetrao tetrix*) and the red crossbill (*Loxia curvirostra*), and cliffs as habitats of choughs, rock pigeon (*Columba livia*) and falcons (*Falco peregrinus*). Permanent streams favored mixed and deciduous forest biotopes for the black woodpecker (*Dryocopus martius*), hawfinch (*Coccothraustes coccothraustes*), wood pigeon (*Columba palumbus*) and scops owl (*Otus scops*),

and among the mammals shrews (*Sorex*, *Neomys*, *Crocidura*), wood mouse (*Apodemus*), bank vole (*Myodes glareolus*) and dormice (*Dryomys*, *Glis*, *Muscardinus*).

The microclimate of the thermal springs near the cave certainly provided local conditions that were highly favorable as a biotope for autochthonous deciduous forest-dwelling small vertebrates and attractive as drinking, feeding or comfort places for local species. Thus, the warm ponds increased the regional habitat complexity and led to a greater prey diversity of the eagle owls (*Bubo bubo*) than would have been recorded without these. To the south, within the transient area of the plain of Almopia, grass and scrub land, rich in sheltering vegetation, can be reconstructed where temperate “extant Mediterranean” faunal elements like brown hares (*Lepus europaeus*) could live, as well as more continental elements like the black francolin (*Francolinus francolinus*), grey partridge (*Perdix perdix*), the calandra lark (*Melanocorypha calandra*) and the little owl (*Athene noctua*), the Romanian and the migratory hamsters (*Cricetulus*, *Mesocricetus*), sousliks (*Spermophilus citellus*), voles (*Microtus*, *Myodes*, *Arvicola*) and the lesser blind mole-rat (*Spalax leucodon*). The fish remains of the LAC Ia assemblage are not yet studied, but they testify to the predation of the owls along water streams or ponds, as the remains of the white-throated dipper (*Cinclus cinclus*) in the taphocoenosis do. This species is an indicator of fast-flowing small creeks and streams in places with rocky bottoms, characteristic of the upper and middle reaches of rivers in the area. The bird species spectrum does not contain any waterfowl, which inhabit mainly lower reaches and larger steady water bodies.. The foreland Nisi fan wetlands with their Late Glacial record (Lawson *et al.*, 2005) and reconstructed habitats for aquatic birds are ~20 km away from the Loutra Almopia Cave. We suppose that these habitats were definitely outside the predation radius of the LAC Ia eagle owls.

Quaternary research in the southern Balkans and the northern Aegean region brought fine-scale results of a rather cold and dry climate during the early part of the Late Glacial, ~19–~14.7 cal kyrs BP (“late Pleniglacial” in Kotthoff *et al.*, 2011) and of the later rather humid Bølling–Allerød interstadial, ~14.7–12.8 kyrs BP (*e.g.*, as indicated by Kennett *et al.*, 2015) with expanded temperate woodland as well as of the dryer stadial climatic conditions close to and during the Younger Dryas, when open steppe communities in the region again extended (Bottema, 1995; Lawson *et al.*, 2004, 2005; Aufgebauer *et al.*, 2012; Psomiadis *et al.*, 2014). Based on the analysis of the geographically closest Late Glacial

pollen profiles to the LAC Ia site, from the Agra Nisi wetlands, also for the deepest parts a lightly wooded landscape with varying amounts of deciduous trees is reconstructed; *Pinus* expanded significantly during the interstadial, but *Quercus* and even thermophilous trees as the hop hornbeam (*Ostrya carpinifolia/Carpinus orientalis*) and the manna ash (*Fraxinus ornus*) were present (Lawson *et al.*, 2005). Further pollen and proxy data from lake sediments in the SW Balkans show montane deciduous forests with thermophilous species rather continuously during the Late Glacial (Panagiotopoulos *et al.*, 2014). According to a recent quantitative paleoprecipitation estimate model study in the later Younger Dryas (Rea *et al.*, 2020, figs 2, 3), a higher annual precipitation rate than the actual seems plausible in the Voras mountain range.

Among the LAC Ia eagle owl's prey, we find species that, in the Balkans today, are migratory and stay only during the breeding season: *Otus scops*, *Sylvia cf. borin*, *Caprimulgus* sp., *Hirundo* sp. and *Riparia/Ptyonoprogne*. It is noteworthy that these migrants are very few compared to year-round resident species or winter migrants. They make up only five of the total 68 established taxa or 7.3%. The weak presence of summer migrants is probably an indication of the relatively more expressed “boreal” phenomena under the conditions of a relatively cooler climate, characteristic of the stadials. On the other hand, the presence of these species unequivocally marks the functioning of the site as a feeding ground during the summer season, at least during part of the period of its existence.

Five bird taxa, *Buteo* sp. cf. *B. lagopus*, *Melanocorypha calandra*, *Melanocorypha* sp., *Bombicilla garrulus* and *Plectrophenax* cf. *P. nivalis*, which are 7.3% of the species composition, breed today in the boreal zone and are winter guests in the southern Balkans. As the paleoecological and chronological results speak in favor of stadial or close to stadial conditions, it cannot be excluded that these species may also have been resident in the Voras Mountains. Thus, their presence in the cave does not prove that the eagle owls used also the site during the cold season. With such an equalization of these two groups of birds, it turns out that the remaining majority of bird species (58), 85.3%, are birds that have the same type of residence, i.e., resident as the extant populations of bird species of the Balkans.

Concerning the habitats of the three lagomorph species, the ranges of pikas and mountain hares did very probably overlap. Habitats of mountain hares are most plausible in the mid-altitudes and slopes of the Voras Mountains, and those of brown hares

in or close to the Almopia plain. Hybrids of the two species must be considered possible, where their habitats overlap, as introgression of genes from one into the other species' genome is testified (Thulin *et al.*, 1997; Melo-Ferreira *et al.*, 2007; Zachos *et al.*, 2010; Pohjoismäki *et al.*, 2021). Until now, however, no molecular signature of ancestral mountain hare introgressions in modern brown hares from the Balkans have been detected (Djan *et al.*, 2017). Concerning the latest Pleistocene or early Holocene extinction of the Balkan mountain hare, the more pronounced adaptability of the competing brown hare provides a reasonable model, as individuals are recently observed in the Alps up to altitudes of 2,300 m in the former habitat of mountain hares (Schenker *et al.*, 2020). Stable brown hare populations of the Balkans during the late Late Pleistocene may have been responsible for the re-population of Central Europe after the Late Glacial (compare Stamatis *et al.*, 2009; Miracle *et al.*, 2010).

Acknowledgements

The Austrian Academy of Sciences (Herwig Friesinger, head of the former Prehistoric Commission, and the Scientific Exchange Program) and Evangelia Tsoukala (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, School of Geology) granted travel costs for FAF. Besides this, the authors did not receive any other specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors. The Natural History Museum of Vienna (1st Zoological Department and the Department of Geology and Paleontology) provided comparison material. Thanks to Franz Suchentrunk (Research Institute of Wildlife Ecology, University of Veterinary Medicine Vienna, Department of Integrative Biology and Evolution) for most important discussions, reviewing an early draft of the paper and furnishing the paper with the analysis of the palatal bridge cranial fragment. Erika Gál (Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Budapest) and Borut Toškan (Research Center of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Ljubljana) provided important literature. Evangelos Vlachos (School of Geology, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece) and CONICET and Museo Paleontológico Egidio Feruglio, Trelew, Argentina did editorial handling of figures. Nikos Vasileiadis and Pavlos Piskoulis were great partners during the cave excursion in 2017. We thank Vincenzo Pentecari (Spanish National Research Council – CSIC, Biodiversity Research Institute – IMIB at Oviedo) for immediate response concerning the use of deep cave parts by eagle owls, and Georgios Lazaridis

(Faculty of Geology of Aristotle University) for his thorough speleological comments on the site. Finally, we thank Steve Smith (Konrad-Lorenz-Institute of Ethology, Department of Interdisciplinary Life Sciences, University of Veterinary Medicine, Vienna) and two anonymous reviewers for their responsible reading and improvement of the paper.

APPENDIX A

List of Lagomorpha specimens from the Loutra Almopias Cave

All specimens are from LAC Ia, other chambers are indicated in parentheses.

Ochotona pusilla:

Teeth: 6 I dex: LAC 19793, 19811, 19815, 19816, 19817, 19827. 6 I sin: LAC 17468 (LAC III), 19812, 19813, 19814, 19818, 19820. P2 dex: LAC 19834. DP3 dex: LAC 19833. 3 P4 dex: LAC 17819 (LAC III), 19809, 19810. P3 dex: LAC 19822. P3 sin: LAC 19821. P3 fr sin: LAC 19826. P4/M1 dex: LAC 19823. 2 P4/M1 sin: LAC 18931, 19828. M2 dex: LAC 19836. 4 M2 sin: LAC 19830, 19831, 19837, 19838. i dex: LAC 19805. dp3 dex: LAC 19857. 3 dp3 sin: LAC 19854, 19855, 19856. dp4 dex: LAC 19859. 3 dp4 sin: LAC 16892 (LAC II), 19260 (LAC III), 19858. dp4 fr sin: LAC 17395 (LAC III). p3 dex: LAC 19829. p3 sin: LAC 19835. 3 p4/m1,2 dex: LAC 18954, 19534, 19824. p4/m1,2 sin: LAC 19832. Postcranial material (not labelled): Ul prox+dia, Ti prox, Mp prox+dia, Mp complete.

Lepus timidus: I dex LAC 18923, P2 dex: LAC 18919, p3 dex: LAC 18944. Cranial fragment (palatal): LAC 3875

Lepus cf. timidus p3 sin: LAC 18945, Ph2 pes dig V dex: LAC 1875, 2 Ph2 pes: LAC 1876, 1877

Lepus europaeus:

I dex: LAC 19794, I sin: LAC 18922, 3 i dex LAC 19780, LAC 19806, LAC 19808, 2 i sin LAC 19801, LAC 19807, P2 dex: LAC 18918, P2 sin: LAC 19819, p3 dex: LAC 19796, 3 p3 sin: LAC 17099 (LAC II), 18946, 19782

Lepus cf. europaeus: 2 p3 sin: LAC 19781, 19783, Nav sin: LAC 3858, Cub sin: LAC 3859

Lepus sp. (findings without diagnostic species characteristics):

Teeth: i dex (juvenile) LAC 19805, P2 dex: LAC 18920. 2 P2 sin: LAC 19795, 19825. p3sin LAC 19783. Mx fr: LAC 4584.

Postcranial: Hu sin: LAC 7501a (LAC III), Hu dist dex: LAC 3802, Hu dist sin: LAC 3817, Hu dia dex: LAC 7230, Fe dex: LAC 5124h, Fe prox+dia dex: LAC5124k, Fe caput dex: LAC 3818, Ul prox dex: LAC 4323, Ti prox+dist dex: LAC 5124g, 3 Ti dist+dia dex: LAC 3819, 5253a, 7501b (LAC Ib), Ti dist dex: LAC 3803, 3 Ti dist sin: LAC 3879 (AMS dated sample), 3881, 3882, 2 Ti dia sin: LAC 3880, 5124j, Pa dex?: LAC 3961, Ses/Pa: LAC 4583, As fr sin: LAC 3857, 5 Cal dex: LAC 3804, 3805, 3806, 3807, 3877, Cal sin: LAC 3878, McII prox dex: 1881, McIV prox dex: 1882, 5 Mc dist: 1883, 1885, 1886, 1887, 1888, 2 MtII prox dex: LAC 3808, 4325, 2 MtII prox sin: LAC 3809, 3886, MtIII sin: LAC 3883, 2 MtIII prox dex: LAC 3884, 4324, 2 MtIV prox dex: LAC 3811, 3813, MtIV sin: LAC 3885, MtIV prox sin: LAC 3812, MtV prox dex: LAC 3810, 4 Mt dist: LAC 1884, 1889, 4585, 4587, Ph1 manus dist: LAC 4586, Ph2 manus dig III?: LAC 3853, 4 Ph1 pes: LAC 1870, 3814, 3815, 4326, 2 Ph1 pes prox: LAC 1871, 1872, 2 Ph1 pes dist: LAC 1873, 1874, Ph2 pes dig II dex: LAC 3836, Vertebra lumbalis: LAC 5598, 2 Cox dex: LAC 3876, 4322, Cox fr dex: LAC 3800, Cox fr sin: LAC 7229.

APPENDIX B

A wild rabbit find from LAC I

A complete right upper humerus from *Oryctolagus cuniculus* (L., 1758) (LAC 5000, collection of the

Natural History Museum of Aridaia) reported from the LAC I floor has a (sub)recent appearance. The total length is 72.2 mm. Published measurements of the European wild rabbits range around a mean value of 64.7 mm (specimens from Austria in Fladerer, 1984). This is, as an approximate mean, consistent with numerous materials from France, Spain and Portugal (Callou, 2003) that show lengths between 50.6 mm and 71.3 mm.

The humerus has no distinct bite or gnaw marks, and it is very probable that it is a remnant from a snack episode by humans. The intimate rocky area around the cave and the foothills of the Voras Mountains can be excluded as a rabbit habitat, and introduction from outside this area must be assumed.

Oryctolagus cuniculus was confined to the Iberian Peninsula and Southern France during the Late Pleistocene and Postglacial (Lopez-Martinez, 2008). The species has been introduced in some parts of Europe during the Bronze age, but first introduction observations, and hence hypothetical transportation, is attributed to the Phoenicians around 1,000 BC (Monnerot *et al.*, 1994). It is not expected to be found in Greco-Roman settlements of the Southern Balkans before the second half of the first millennium BC (Hemmer, 1990). It is regarded as a Late Holocene anthropogenic element on Ionian and Aegean islands (Masseti, 1998, 2012). Even a recent survey does not report wild rabbits from the central or southern Balkans, including the Greek mainland (Villafuerte and Delibes-Mateos, 2019).

REFERENCES

- Andrews, P. 1990. *Owls, Caves, and Fossils. Predation, Preservation and Accumulation of Small Mammal Bones in Caves, with an Analysis of the Pleistocene Cave Faunas from Westbury-sub-Mendip, Somerset, UK*. Natural History Museum Publications, London, 231 pp.
- Angermann, R. 1966. Beiträge zur Kenntnis der Gattung *Lepus* (Lagomorpha, Leporidae). I. Abgrenzung der Gattung *Lepus*. *Mitteilungen des Zoologischen Museums, Berlin* 42, 127–144.
- Aufgebauer, A., Panagiotopoulos, K., Wagner, B., Schaebitz, F., Viehberg, F.A., Vogel, H., Zanchetta, G., Sulpizio, R., Leng, M.J., Damaschke, M. 2012. Climate and environmental change in the Balkans over the last 17ka recorded in sediments from Lake Prespa (Albania/F.Y.R. of Macedonia/Greece). *Quaternary International* 274, 122–135, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2012.02.015>.
- Averianov, A. 2001. Pleistocene lagomorphs of Eurasia. *Deinsea* 8, 1–13.
- Barone, R., Pavaux, C., Blin, P.C., Cuq, P. 1973. *Atlas d'anatomie du lapin*. Paris, 219 pp.
- Bocheński, Z. 2005. Owls, diurnal raptors and humans: signatures on avian bones. In: O'Connor, T. (Ed.), *Biosphere to Lithosphere. New Studies in Vertebrate Taphonomy*. Oxford Books, Oxford, 31–45.
- Bocheński, Z., Tomek, T., Boev, Z., Mitev, I. 1993. Patterns of bird bone fragmentation in pellets of the Tawny Owl (*Strix aluco*) and the Eagle Owl (*Bubo bubo*) and their taphonomic implications. *Acta Zoologica Cracoviensia* 36 (2), 313–328.
- Boev, Z., Tsoukala, E. 2019. Late Pleistocene and Earliest Holocene avifauna from the Loutra Almopias Cave (Macedonia, Greece). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 40, 1–31, <https://doi.org/10.48027/hnb.40.01001>.
- Bogičević, K., Dimitrijević, V. 2004. Quaternary fauna from Mališina stijena near Pljevlja (Montenegro). *Zbornik radova Odbora za kras i speleologiju, SANU, Beograd* 8, 119–133.
- Bottema, S. 1995. The Younger Dryas in the Eastern Mediterranean. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 14 (9), 883–891, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-3791\(95\)00069-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-3791(95)00069-0).

- Bronk Ramsey, C. 2009. Bayesian analysis of radiocarbon dates. *Radiocarbon* 51 (1), 337–360.
- Bronk Ramsey, C. 2021. <https://c14.arch.ox.ac.uk/oxcal/Ox-Cal.html> – the newest online version of Bronk Ramsey, C. 2009.
- Callou, C. 2003. De la garenne au clapier: étude archéozoologique du Lapin en Europe occidentale. *Mémoires du Muséum national d'histoire naturelle* 189, 358 pp.
- Carlson, A.E. 2013. The Younger Dryas Climate Event. In: Elias, S.A. (Ed.), *The Encyclopedia of Quaternary Science* 3, Elsevier, 126–134, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-53643-3.00029-7>.
- Chatzopoulou, K. 2003. The Late Pleistocene small mammal fauna from Loutra Aridea Bear-Cave (Pella, Macedonia, Greece). Additional Data. *Atti del Museo Civico di Storia Naturale di Trieste* 49 (Suppl.), 35–45.
- Chatzopoulou, K. 2005. The stratigraphy from the Loutra Arideas Bear-Cave (Pella, Macedonia, Greece) with emphasis on two new chambers. *Proceedings of the 14th International Congress of Speleology, Kalamos Athens 1*, 49–51.
- Chatzopoulou, K. 2014. *The micromammals of the Quaternary deposits from cave A, Loutra Almopias (Pella, Northern Greece)*. Stratigraphy-Taphonomy-Paleoenvironment. PhD thesis, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Annex Number of the Scientific Annals of the School of Geology 166, 377 pp.
- Chatzopoulou, K., Tsoukala, E., Vlachos, E. 2011. The contribution of Late Pleistocene micromammalian fauna in the Interpretation of the taphonomical history of the Loutra Almopias Cave (Macedonia, Greece). In: Horáček, I., Wagner, J., Čermák, S. (Eds), *Late Cenozoic Mammals: Fossil Record, Biostratigraphy, Paleocology, Praha 16–19 May 2011*, Abstract Book, 1–2.
- Dawson, M.R., 1958. Later Tertiary leporids of North America. *University of Kansas Paleontological Contributions* 6, 1–75.
- De Cupere, B., Thys, S., Van Neer, W., Ervynck, A., Corremans, M., Waelkens, M. 2009. Eagle owl (*Bubo bubo*) pellets from Roman Sagalassos (SW Turkey): distinguishing the prey remains from nest and roost sites. *International Journal of Osteoarchaeology* 19 (1), 1–22, <https://doi.org/10.1002/oa.965>.
- Denys, C., Stotzel, E., Andrews, P., Bailon, S., Rihane, A., Huchet, J.B., Fernandez-Jalvo, Y., Laroulandie, V. 2018. Taphonomy of small predators multi-taxa accumulations: palaeoecological implications. *Historical Biology* 30 (6), 868–881, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08912963.2017.1347647>.
- Dimitrijević, V. 1988. The first finding of steppe pika (*Ochotona pusilla* Pallas) in Serbia. *Annales géologiques de la Péninsule balkanique* 51, 379–389 (in Serbo-Croatian, with English summary).
- Dimitrijevic, V. 1991. Quaternary mammals of the Smolučka Cave in Southwest Serbia. *Paleontologija Jugoslavije, Jugoslovenska Akademija Znanosti I Umetnosti* 41, 1–88.
- Dimitrijević, V. 1997. Upper Pleistocene mammals from cave deposits of Serbia. *Annales géologiques de la Péninsule balkanique* 61 (2), 179–370.
- Dimitrijević, V.M., Jovanović, K.I. 2002. Kvarterni sisari iz Mirilovske pećine kod Čuprije (Istočna Srbija). *Zbornik radova Odbora za kras i speleologiju* 7, 113–125.
- Döppes, D., Rabeder, G. (Eds) 1997. Pliozäne und pleistozäne Faunen Österreichs. Ein Katalog der wichtigsten Fossilfundstellen und ihrer Faunen. *Mitteilungen der Kommission für Quartärforschung, Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften* 10, 267 pp.
- Dumitrescu, M., Samson, P., Terzea, E., Radulescu, C., Ghica, M. 1963. Pestera ‘La Adam’, statiune pleistocena. *Lucrarile Institutul de Speologie ‘Emil Racovitza’* 1–2, 229–284.
- Djan, M., Stefanović, M., Veličković, N., Lavandinović, V., Alves, P., Suchentrunk, F. 2017. Brown hares (*Lepus europaeus* Palas, 1778) from the Balkans: a refined phylogeographic model. *Hystrix, the Italian Journal of Mammalogy* 28 (2), 186–193, <https://doi.org/10.4404/hystrix-28.2-12202>.
- Eleftheriadis, G. 2006. The Geology of Almopia Sepeleopark. *Scientific Annals, School of Geology Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), Special Volume* 98, 27–31.
- Erbajeva, M.A., Curren, A. 2003. *Ochotona spelea* Owen, 1846: A new look at the taxonomic position. In: Petculescu, A., Ştiucă, E. (Eds), *Advances in Vertebrate Paleontology “Hen to Panta”*, Romanian Academy “Emil Racovitza”, Institute of Speleology, Bucharest, 97–104.
- Erbajeva, M., Montuire, S., Chaline, J. 2001. New ochotonids (Lagomorpha) from the Pleistocene of France. *Geodiversitas* 23 (3), 395–409.
- Fladerer, F.A. 1984. Das Vordergliedmaßenskelett von *Hypolagus beremendensis* und von *Lepus* sp. (Lagomorpha, Mammalia) aus dem Altpleistozän von Deutsch-Altenburg. *Beiträge zur Paläontologie von Österreich* 11, 71–148.
- Fladerer, F.A. 1987. Beitrag zur Entwicklung von *Hypolagus* und *Lepus* (Lagomorpha, Mammalia) im Pliopleistozän von Mitteleuropa. *Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften Mathematisch-Naturwissenschaftliche Klasse, Sitzungsberichte Abteilung I* 196, 123–138.
- Fladerer, F.A. 1992. Neue Funde von Steppenfeifhasen (*Ochotona pusilla* PALLAS) und Schneehasen (*Lepus timidus* L.) im Spätglazial der Ostalpen. *Mitteilungen der Kommission für Quartärforschung, Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften* 8, 189–209 (in German, with English summary).
- Fladerer, F.A. 2000. Late Quaternary vertebrate taphocoenoses from cave deposits in southeastern Austria. In: Hart, M.B. (Ed.), *Climates: Past and Present*. Geological Society Special Publications 181, 199–213, <https://doi.org/10.1144/GSL.SP.2000.181.01.18>.
- Fladerer, F.A., Salcher-Jedrasiak, T. 2008. Archäozoologische und taphonomische Untersuchungen. In: Neugebauer-Maresch, C. (Ed.), *Krems-Hundssteig – Mammutjägerlager der Eiszeit. Ein Nutzungsareal paläolithischer Jäger- und Sammler(innen) vor 41.000–27.000 Jahren*. *Mitteilungen der prähistorischen Kommission, Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften* 67, 216–312.
- Fostowicz-Frelik, Ł. 2007. The hind limb skeleton and cursorial adaptations of the Plio-Pleistocene rabbit *Hypolagus beremendensis*. *Acta Palaeontologica Polonica* 52 (3), 447–476.
- Fostowicz-Frelik, Ł., Frelik, G.J. 2010. The earliest occurrence of the steppe pika (*Ochotona pusilla*) in Europe near the Pliocene/Pleistocene boundary. *Naturwissenschaften* 97, 325–329. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00114-009-0634-6>.
- Fostowicz-Frelik, Ł., Gasparik, M. 2006. The taxonomic status of leporid remains from Ördöglyuk Cave, Solymár (Hungary). *Acta Zoologica Cracoviensia* 49A (1–2), 151–161, <https://doi.org/10.3409/00000006783995490>.
- Hacklander, K., Schai-Braun, S. 2019. *Lepus europaeus*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species in 2019: e.T41280A45187424, www.iucnredlist.org (accessed on 20 January 2022).
- Hauser, W. 1921. Osteologische Unterscheidungsmerkmale der schweizerischen Feld und Alpenhasen (*Lepus europaeus*

- Pall. und *Lepus medius varronis* Miller.). *Zeitschrift für induktive Abstammungs- und Vererbungslehre* 26, 32–108, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01715468>.
- Heggøy, O., Aarvak, T., Ranke, P.S., Solheim, R., Øien, I.J. 2021. Home range and excursive post-breeding movements of Eurasian eagle-owls revealed by GPS Satellite Transmitters. *Journal of Raptor Research* 55 (4), 619–626, <https://doi.org/10.3356/JRR-19-95>.
- Hemmer, H. 1990. *Domestication: The decline of environmental appreciation*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 277 pp.
- Hibbard, C.W. 1963. The origin of the P₃ pattern of *Sylvilagus*, *Caprolagus*, *Oryctolagus* and *Lepus*. *Journal of Mammalogy* 44 (1), 1–15, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1377162>.
- Hockett, B., Haws, J.A. 2002. Taphonomic and methodological perspectives of leporid hunting during the Upper Paleolithic of the Western Mediterranean Basin. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 9, 269–302, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1019503030246>.
- Hughes, P.D. 2004. *Quaternary glaciation in the Pindus Mountains, Northwest Greece*. PhD thesis, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, 341 pp.
- Hughes, P.D., Woodward J.C., Gibbard, P.L. 2006. The last glaciers of Greece. *Zeitschrift für Geomorphologie* 50 (1), 37–61, <https://doi.org/10.1127/zfg/50/2006/37>.
- Jánossy, D. 1969. Stratigraphische Auswertung der europäischen mittelpleistozänen Wirbeltierfauna. Teil II. *Berichte der Deutschen Gesellschaft für geologische Wissenschaften, Reihe A: Geologie und Paläontologie* 14, 573–634.
- Jánossy, D., 1986. *Pleistocene Vertebrate Faunas of Hungary*. Elsevier, Amsterdam–Oxford–New York–Tokyo, 208 pp.
- Jánossy, D., Schmidt, E. 1970. Die Nahrung des Uhus (*Bubo bubo*). Regionale und erdzeitliche Änderungen. *Bonner Zoologische Beiträge* 21, 25–51.
- Kabourolglou, E.M., Chatzitheodorou, T. 1999. Geomorphological changes and sedimentation in the cave A (Agiasma) of Loutraki (Pella, Macedonia, Greece). In: Hellenic Geographical Society (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 5th Pan-Hellenic Geographical Congress. Athens, Vol. 1*, 83–93 (in Greek).
- Kennett, J.P., Kennett, D.J., Culleton, B.J., Tortosa, J.E.A., Bischoff, J.L., Bunch, T.E., Daniel, I.R., Erlandson, J.M., Ferraro, D., Firestone, R.B., Goodyear, A.C., Israde-Alcántara, I., Johnson, J.R., Jordá Pardo, J.F., Kimbel, D.R., LeCompte, M.A., Lopinot, N.H., Mahaney, W.C., Moore, A.M.T., Moore, C.R., Ray, J.H., Stafford, T.W., Tankersley, K.B., Wittke, J.H., Wolbach, W.S., West, A. 2015. Bayesian chronological analyses consistent with synchronous age of 12,835–12,735 Cal B.P. for Younger Dryas boundary on four continents. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 112 (32), E4344–E4353, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1507146112>.
- Koby, F.E. 1959. Contribution au diagnostic ostéologique différentiel de *Lepus timidus* Linné et *L. europaeus* Pallas. *Verhandlungen der Naturforschenden Gesellschaft in Basel* 70, 19–44.
- Koby, F.E. 1960. Contribution à la connaissance des lièvres fossiles, principalement de ceux de la dernière glaciation. *Verhandlungen der Naturforschenden Gesellschaft in Basel* 71, 149–173.
- Kotthoff, U., Koutsodendrīs, A., Pross, J., Schmiedl, G., Bornemann, A., Kaul, C., Marino, G., Peyron, O., Schiebel, R. 2011. Impact of Lateglacial cold events on the Northern Aegean Region reconstructed from marine and terrestrial proxy data. *Journal of Quaternary Science* 26 (1), 86–96, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.1430>.
- Kuhlemann, J., Milivojević, M., Krumrei, I., Kubik, P.W. 2009. Last glaciation of the Šara Range (Balkan peninsula): Increasing dryness from the LGM to the Holocene. *Austrian Journal of Earth Sciences* 102, 146–158.
- Laplana, C., Sevilla, P., Arsuaga, J.L., Arriaza, M.C., Baquedano, E., Pérez-González, A., López-Martínez, N. 2015. How far into Europe did pikas (Lagomorpha: Ochotonidae) go during the Pleistocene? New evidence from Central Iberia. *PLoS ONE* 10 (11): e0140513, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0140513>.
- Lazaridis, G., Melfos, V. 2021. Morphological features and formation conditions of The Almopia Speleopark caves (Loutra Almopias, N. Greece). *Acta Carsologica* 50 (1), 37–48, <https://doi.org/10.3986/ac.v50i1.7592>.
- Lawson, I.T., Frogley, M., Bryant, C., Preece, R., Tzedakis, P. 2004. The Lateglacial and Holocene environmental history of the Ioannina basin, north-west Greece. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 23 (14–15), 1599–1625, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2004.02.003>.
- Lawson, I.T., Al-Omari, S., Tzedakis, P.C., Bryant, C.L., Christianis, K. 2005. Lateglacial and Holocene vegetation history at Nisi Fen and the Boras mountains, northern Greece. *The Holocene* 15 (6), 873–887, <https://doi.org/10.1191/2F0959683605h1860ra>.
- Lloveras, L., Moreno-García, M., Nadal, J. 2009. The eagle owl (*Bubo bubo*) as a leporid remains accumulator: taphonomic analysis of modern rabbit remains recovered from nests of this predator. *International Journal of Osteoarchaeology* 19 (5), 573–592, <https://doi.org/10.1002/oa.995>.
- Lloveras, L., Moreno-García, M., Nadal, J. 2012. Assessing the variability in taphonomic studies of modern leporid remains from Eagle Owl (*Bubo bubo*) nest assemblages: the importance of age of prey. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 39 (12), 3754–3764, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2012.06.033>.
- Longin, R. 1971. New method of collagen extraction for radiocarbon dating. *Nature* 230, 241–242, <https://doi.org/10.1038/230241a0>.
- López-Martínez, N. 1974. *Évolution de la lignée Piezodus-Prolagus (Lagomorpha Ochotonidae) dans le Cénozoïque d'Europe sud-occidentale*. Thèse Dr. Sp. Paléontologie, Université des sciences et techniques du Languedoc, 153 pp., 16 figs., 34 graphs, 18 pls.
- López-Martínez, N. 1980. Les lagomorphs (Mammalia) du pléistocène supérieur de Jaurens. *Nouvelles Archives du Museum d'Histoire Naturelle de Lyon* 18, 5–16, <https://doi.org/10.3406/mhnl.1980.1044>.
- López-Martínez, N. 2008. The lagomorph fossil record and the origin of the European rabbit. In: Alves, P.C., Ferrand, N., Hackländer, K. (Eds), *Lagomorph Biology: Evolution, Ecology, and Conservation*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 27–46.
- López-Martínez, N., Thaler, L. 1975. Biogéographie, evolution et complements à la systématique du groupe d'Ochotonides *Piezodus-Prolagus* (Mammalia, Lagomorpha). *Bulletin de la Société géologique de France, 7^{ème} série* 17 (5), 850–866.
- Lourenço, L. 2006. The food habits of European Eagle Owls in Southern Portugal. *Journal of Raptor Research* 40 (4), 297–300, [https://doi.org/10.3356/0892-016\(2006\)40\[297:TFHOEE\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.3356/0892-016(2006)40[297:TFHOEE]2.0.CO;2).
- Malez, M. 1979. Prilog poznavanju rasprostranjenosti stepske zviždare u gornjem pleistocenu Hrvatske. *Rad Jugoslavenske akademije znanosti i umjetnosti* 383, 345–361.
- Malez, M. 1986. Die quartären Vertebraten-Faunen in der SFR Jugoslawien. *Quartärpaläontologie* 6, 101–117.

- Markov, G. 1951. Les mamifères quaternaires en Bulgarie. *Bulletin de l'Institut Zoologique de l'Académie bulgare des Sciences* 1, 99–199 (in Bulgarian with French summary)
- Marković, Z. 2008. Small mammals (Rodentia and Lagomorpha) from Gradašnica cave (East Serbia). *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum in Belgrade* 1, 65–77.
- Marković, Z., Pavlović, G. 1991. First investigation results for Vrelska cave fauna, Bela Palanka, Serbia. *Annales géologiques de la Péninsule balkanique* 55 (1), 221–230.
- Masseti, M. 1998. Holocene endemic and anthropochorous wild mammals of the Mediterranean islands. *Anthropozoologica* 28, 3–20.
- Masseti, M. 2012. *Atlas of terrestrial mammals of the Ionian and Aegean islands*. De Gruyter, Berlin, 302 pp., <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110254587>.
- Mayhew, D.F. 1978. Late Pleistocene small mammals from Arnissa (Macedonia, Greece). *Proceedings of the Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen B81* (3), 302–321.
- Melo-Ferreira, J., Boursot, P., Randi, E., Kryukov, A., Suchentrunk, F., Ferrand, N., Alves, P.C. 2007. The rise and fall of the mountain hare (*Lepus timidus*) during Pleistocene glaciations: expansion and retreat with hybridization in the Iberian Peninsula. *Molecular Ecology* 16 (3), 605–618, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2006.03166.x>.
- Melentis, I.K. 1969. Die quartären Vertebraten der Höhle der Seen von Kleitoria (Im Gebiet des Aroania-Gebirges). *Praktika Akademias Athinon* 43, 350–363 (in Greek, with German summary).
- Messerli, B. 1967. Die eiszeitliche und die gegenwärtige Vergletscherung im Mittelemeerraum. *Geographica Helvetica* 22, 105–228.
- Mihailović, D. 2009. Upper Palaeolithic and Mesolithic chipped stone industries from Crvena Stijena. In: Srejović, D. (Ed.), *Prehistoric Settlements in Caves and Rock-Shelters of Serbia and Montenegro*. Fascicule I, Center for Archaeological Research, Belgrade, 9–60.
- Miracle, P.T., Brajković, D. 2010. The palaeoecological significance of the Pleistocene mammalian fauna from Veternica Cave, Croatia. Revision of the Lagomorpha, Canidae, Mustelidae and Felidae. *Geologia Croatica* 63 (2), 207–224, <https://doi.org/10.4154/gc.2010.18>.
- Miracle, P.T., Lenardić, J.M., Brajković, D. 2010. Last Glacial Climates, “Refugia”, and Faunal Change in Southeastern Europe: Mammalian Assemblages from Veternica, Velika pećina, and Vindija Caves (Croatia). *Quaternary International* 212 (2), 137–148, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2009.06.003>.
- Mitev, I. 2016. Subfossil fauna of birds and mammals (Aves et Mammalia – Vertebrata) from deposits in Northeastern Bulgaria. In: Boev, Z. (Ed.), *Ivan Mitev – Collected Works, Vol. 1. Bulgarian Nature*. “Logis”, Sofia, 203–691.
- Mitev, I., Boev, Z. 2006. Food spectrum of the Eagle Owl (*Bubo bubo* (L., 1758), Aves: Strigiformes) from two Holocene localities in NE Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 17, 153–165 (in Bulgarian, with English summary).
- Monnerot, M., Vigne, J. D., Biju-Duval, C., Casane, D., Callou, C., Hardy, C., Mougél, F., Soriguer, R., Dennebouy, N., Mounolou, J.C. 1994. Rabbit and man: genetic and historic approach. *Genetics Selection Evolution* 26, Suppl. 1, 167–182, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1297-9686-26-S1-S167>.
- Morel, P., Müller, W. 1997. Hauterive-Champréveyres 11. Un campement magdalénien au bord du lac de Neuchâtel: étude archéozoologique (secteur 1). *Archéologie neuchâteloise* 23, 1–149.
- Mottl, M. 1975. Die pleistozänen Säugetierfaunen und Kulturen des Grazer Berglandes. In: Fügél, H.W. (Ed.), *Die Geologie des Grazer Berglandes (2. Auflage)*. Mitteilungen der Abteilung für Geologie, Paläontologie und Bergbau am Landesmuseum Joanneum, Graz, Sonderheft 1, 159–186.
- Nagel, D., Pacher, M., Tsoukala, E., 2019. Large mammals except cave-bears from the Loutra Almopias Cave, Late Pleistocene, Macedonia, Greece. *Berichte der Geologischen Bundesanstalt* 132, 123–147.
- Nikolov, I. 1983. Some notes on the cave fossil mammalian fauna in Bulgaria. *4th European Regional Conference of Speleology, 22–28 September 1980, Sofia*, 215–218 (in Bulgarian).
- Panagiotopoulos, K., Böhm, A., Leng, M.J., Wagner, B., Schabitz, F. 2014. Climate variability over the last 92 ka in SW Balkans from analysis of sediments from Lake Prespa. *Climate of the Past* 10 (2), 643–660, <https://doi.org/10.5194/cp-10-643-2014>.
- Papageorgiou, N.K., Vlachos, C.G., Bakaloudis, D.E. 1993. Diet and nest site characteristics of Eagle Owl (*Bubo bubo*) breeding in two different habitats in north-eastern Greece. *Avocetta* 17, 49–54.
- Pappa, S., Tsoukala, E., Lazaridis, G., Rabeder, G. 2005. Milk teeth of Quaternary carnivores from northern Greek caves – preliminary report. In: Naturhistorische Gesellschaft Nürnberg e.V. (Ed.), *Neue Forschungen zum Höhlenbären in Europa Abhandlung* 45, 169–182.
- Piskoulis, I.P. 2021. *Quaternary Chiroptera (Mammalia) from Loutra Almopias Cave A (Pella, Macedonia, Greece) – Systematics, phylogenetic relationships, biogeography, palaeoenvironment*. PhD thesis, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Annex Number of the Scientific Annals of the School of Geology 217, 303 pp.
- Piskoulis, P., Chatzopoulou, K. 2022. The fossil record of bats (Mammalia: Chiroptera) in Greece. In: Vlachos, E. (Ed.), *Fossil Vertebrates of Greece – A Synopsis of the Fossil Record and Taxonomy, Vol. 2*. Springer, New York, 93–111.
- Penteriani, V., Gallardo, M., Roche, P., Cazassus, H. 2001. Effects of landscape spatial structure and composition on the settlement of the Eagle Owl *Bubo bubo* in a Mediterranean habitat. *Ardea* 89, 331–340.
- Pohjoismäki, J.L.O., Michell, C., Levänen, R., Smith, S. 2021. Hybridization with mountain hares increases the functional allelic repertoire in brown hares. *Scientific Reports* 11, 15771, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-95357-0>.
- Popov, R. 1908. A contribution to the prehistory of Bulgaria. *Sbornik za narodni umotvorenia* 24, 1–18 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1909. Kodzha-Dermenska mound. A contribution to the prehistory of Bulgaria. *Periodichesko spisanie* 21, 502–562 + 26 pls (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, V.V. 1989. Middle Pleistocene small mammals (Insectivora, Lagomorpha, Rodentia) from Morovitsa Cave (North Bulgaria). *Acta Zoologica Cracoviensia* 32 (13), 561–588.
- Popov, V.V. 1994. Quaternary small mammals from deposits in Temnata-Prohodna Cave system. In: Kozłowski, J.K., Laville, H., Ginter, B. (Eds), *Temnata Cave. Excavations in Karlukovo Karst Area, Bulgaria 1.2*. Jagellonian University Press, Krakow, 9–53.
- Popov, V.V. 2000. The small mammals (Mammalia: Insectivora, Chiroptera, Lagomorpha, Rodentia) from Cave 16 and the paleoenvironmental changes during the Late Pleistocene. In: Ginter, B., Kozłowski, J.K., Gdelli, J.-L., Laville, H. (Eds), *Temnata Cave. Excavation in Karlukovo*

- Karst Area, Bulgaria 2.1. Jagellonian University Press, Krakow, 159–240.
- Psomiadis, D., Ghilardi, M., Demory, F., Delanghe-Sabatier, D., Bloemendal, J., Yiu, C. 2014. Late Pleistocene to mid-Holocene landscape reconstruction in the western part of the Thessaloniki Plain, Greece: evidence for environmental changes, and implications for human occupation. *Zeitschrift für Geomorphologie* 58, Suppl. 2, 67–87.
- Rabeder, G., Tsoukala, E., Kavcik, N. 2006. Chronological and systematic position of cave bears from Loutrá Aridéas (Pella, Macedonia, Greece). *Scientific Annals, School of Geology, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), Special volume* 98, 69–73.
- Rabiniak, E., Rekovets, L., Stewart, J.R., Dalén, L., Barton, N., Strzala, T., Barkaszi, Z., Kovalchuk, O. 2023. Late Pleistocene and Holocene pikas (Mammalia, Lagomorpha) from Europe and the validity of *Ochotona spelaea*: New insights based on mtDNA analysis. *Palaeontologia Electronica* 26 (1): a3, <https://doi.org/10.26879/1241>.
- Rehnus, M., Bollmann, K., Schmatz, D.R., Hackländer, K., Braunisch, V. 2018. Alpine glacial relict species losing out to climate change: The case of the fragmented mountain hare population (*Lepus timidus*) in the Alps. *Global Change Biology* 24 (7), 3236–3253, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14087>.
- Rea, B.R., Pellitero, R., Spagnolo, M., Hughes, P., Ivy-Ochs, S., Renssen, H., Ribolini, A., Bakke, J., Lukas, S., Braithwaite, R.J. 2020. Atmospheric circulation over Europe during the Younger Dryas. *Science Advances* 6, eaba4844, <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aba4844>.
- Reimer, P., Austin, W., Bard, E., Bayliss, A., Blackwell, P., Bronk Ramsey, C., Butzin, M., Cheng, H., Edwards, R., Friedrich, M., Grootes, P., Guilderson, T., Hajdas, I., Heaton, T., Hogg, A., Hughen, K., Kromer, B., Manning, S., Muscheler, R., Palmer, J., Pearson, C., van der Plicht, J., Reimer, R., Richards, D., Scott, E., Southon, J., Turney, C., Wacker, L., Adolphi, F., Büntgen, U., Capano, M., Fahrni, S., Fogtmann-Schulz, A., Friedrich, R., Köhler, P., Kudsk, S., Miyake, F., Olsen, J., Reinig, F., Sakamoto, M., Sookdeo, A., Talamo, S. 2020. The IntCal20 Northern Hemisphere radiocarbon age calibration curve (0–55 cal kBP). *Radiocarbon* 62 (4), 725–757, <https://doi.org/10.1017/RDC.2020.41>.
- Rufà, A., Laroulandie, V. 2019. Prey size as a critical factor for bird bone taphonomy in Eagle Owl (*Bubo bubo*) pellets. *Scientific Reports* 9, 19200, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-55721-7>.
- Sándor, A.D., Ionesco, D.T. 2009. Diet of the Eagle Owl (*Bubo bubo*) in Braşov, Romania. *North-Western Journal of Zoology* 5, 170–178.
- Schenker, L., Bollmann, K., Rehnus, M., Brodbeck, S., Gugerli, F. 2020. Hare's affairs: Lessons learnt from a noninvasive genetic monitoring for tracking mountain hare individuals. *Ecology and Evolution* 10 (18), 10150–10166, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.6676>.
- Simeonov, S., Milchev, B., Boev, Z.N. 1998. Study of the Eagle Owl (*Bubo bubo* (L.)) (Aves: Strigiformes) in the Strandzha Mountain (Southeast Bulgaria). II. Food spectrum and trophic specialization. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 50 (2/3), 87–100.
- Smith, A.T., Johnston, C.H., Temple, H. 2010. *Lepus timidus*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species in 2008: e.T11791A3307029, www.iucnredlist.org (accessed on 20 January 2022).
- Smith, A.T., Lissovsky, A. 2016. *Ochotona pusilla*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2016: e.T15052A45179445, www.iucnredlist.org (accessed on 20 January 2022).
- Smith, S., Sandoval-Castellanos, E., Lagerholm, V.K., Napierala, H., Sablin, M., Von Seth, J., Fladerer, F.A., Geronpré, M., Wojtal, P., Miller, R., Stewart, J.R., Dalén, L. 2017. Nonreceding hare lines: genetic continuity since the Late Pleistocene in European mountain hares (*Lepus timidus*). *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 120 (4), 891–908, <https://doi.org/10.1093/biolinnean/blw009>.
- Stamatis, C., Suchentrunk, F., Moutou, K.A., Giacometti, M., Haerer, G., Djan, M., Vapa, L., Vukovic, M., Tvrtkovic, N., Sert, H., Alves, P.C., Mamuris, Z. 2009. Phylogeography of the Brown Hare (*Lepus europaeus*) in Europe: A Legacy of South-Eastern Mediterranean Refugia?. *Journal of Biogeography* 36 (3), 515–528, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2008.02013.x>.
- Steier, P., Dellinger, F., Kutschera, W., Priller, A., Rom, W., Wild, E.M. 2004. Pushing the precision of ¹⁴C measurements with AMS. *Radiocarbon* 46 (1), 5–16, <http://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200039291>.
- Suchentrunk, F., Davidovic, M. 2004. Evaluation of the classification of Indian hares (*Lepus nigricollis*) into the genus *Indolagus* Gureev, 1953 (Leporidae, Lagomorpha). *Mammalian Biology* 69 (1), 46–57, <https://doi.org/10.1078/1616-5047-115>.
- Suchentrunk, F., Willing, R., Hartl, G.B. 1994. Non-metrical polymorphism of the first lower premolar (P₃) in Austrian brown hares (*Lepus europaeus*): a study on regional differentiation. *Journal of Zoology* 232 (1), 79–91, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7998.1994.tb01560.x>.
- Svoboda, A.J. 2008. The Předmostí area: spatial structure, stratigraphy and chronology. In: Velemínská, J., Brůžek, J. (Eds), *Early Modern Humans from Předmostí Near Přerov*. Academia, Praha, 131–138.
- Thulin, C.-G. 2003. The distribution of mountain hares *Lepus timidus* in Europe: a challenge from brown hares *Lepus europaeus*?. *Mammal Review* 33 (1), 29–42, <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2907.2003.00008.x>.
- Thulin, C.G., Jaarola, M., Tegelström, H. 1997. The occurrence of mountain hare mitochondrial DNA in wild brown hares. *Molecular Ecology* 6 (5), 463–467, <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-294X.1997.t01-1-00199.x>.
- Tsoukala, E., Rabeder, G. 2005. Cave bears and Late Pleistocene associated faunal remains from Loutra Arideas (Pella, Macedonia, Greece). 15 years of research. *Naturhistorische Gesellschaft Nürnberg* 45, 225–236.
- Tsoukala, E., Chatzopoulou, K., Rabeder, G., Pappa, S., Nagel, D., Withalm, G. 2006. Paleontological and stratigraphical research in Loutra Arideas bear cave (Almopia Speleopark, Pella, Macedonia, Greece). *Proceedings of the 12th Intern. Cave Bear Symposium, Thessaloniki/Aridea, Scientific Annals, School of Geology, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), Special Volume* 98, 41–67.
- Veitschegger, K., Fladerer, F.A., Nagel, D.A. 2015. A Late Pleistocene to Holocene succession of leporid species in the southern Vienna Basin (Austria). *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 14 (5), 403–410, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crpv.2015.05.009>.
- Villafuerte, R., Delibes-Mateos, M. 2019. *Oryctolagus cuniculus* (errata version published in 2020). The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species in 2008: e.T41291A170619657, <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2019-3.RLTS.T41291A170619657.en>.

- Von den Driesch, A. 1976. *A Guide to the Measurement of Animal Bones from Archaeological Sites*. Archaeology Peabody Museum Bulletin 1, Cambridge, 137 pp.
- Wilczyński J., Tomek T., Nadachowski A., Miękina B., Rzebik-Kowalska B., Peresviet-Soltan A., Stworzewicz E., Szyndlar Z., Marciszak A., Lõugas L. 2016. Sarakenos Cave (Greece, Beotia) – faunal record and environmental changes during Pleistocene and Holocene. In: Kaczanowska, M., Kozłowski, J.K., Sampson, A. (Eds), *The Sarakenos Cave at Akraephnion, Boeotia, Greece, Vol. II. The Early Neolithic, the Mesolithic and the Final Palaeolithic*. Polska Akademia Umiejętności, Krakow, 63–80.
- Woodward, J.C., Hamlin, R.H.B., Macklin, M.G., Hughes, P.D., Lewin, J. 2008. Glacial activity and catchment dynamics in northwest Greece: Long-term river behaviour and the slackwater sediment record for the last glacial to interglacial transition. *Geomorphology* 101 (1–2), 44–67, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2008.05.018>.
- Zachos, F.E., Ben Slimen, H., Hackländer, K., Giacometti, M., Suchentrunk, F. 2010. Regional genetic *in situ* differentiation despite phylogenetic heterogeneity in Alpine mountain hares. *Journal of Zoology* 282 (1), 47–53, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7998.2010.00710.x>.